

Carbon Chain Molecules Toward Embedded Low-Mass Protostars

Charles Law

A thesis presented to the Department of Astronomy in partial fulfillment
of the requirements for the degree of Bachelor of Arts

April 7, 2017
Harvard College

Carbon Chain Molecules Toward Embedded Low-Mass Protostars

Charles Law

Abstract

Carbon chain molecules may be an important reservoir of reactive, volatile organics during planet formation. Carbon chains have been observed toward several low-mass young stellar objects (YSOs), but their typical abundances and chemical relationships in such sources are largely unconstrained. We present observations toward 16 deeply embedded (Class 0/I) low-mass protostars using the IRAM 30 m telescope. Carbon chains are found to be common at this stage of protostellar evolution. We detect CCS, CCCS, HC₃N, HC₅N, C₃H, and C₄H toward 94%, 44%, 81%, 38%, 88%, and 88% of sources, respectively. Median column densities derived using survival analysis range between $9.6 \times 10^{10} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ (CCCS) and $1.4 \times 10^{13} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ (C₄H) and fractional abundances with respect to hydrogen range between 1.6×10^{-13} (CCCS) and 4.5×10^{-11} (C₄H). Column densities for each molecule vary by one to two orders of magnitude across the sample. Median abundances in our low-mass YSOs are found to be underabundant compared to cold cloud cores, warm carbon chain chemistry (WCCC) sources, and warm-up models. With the exception of CCS and HC₃N, we do not find significant correlations between molecules in different carbon chain families, indicative of the presence of several independent carbon chain formation chemistries. This correlation also implies that the production chemistry of sulfur-bearing carbon chains and cyanopolyynes, which are closely related in the cold cloud phase, continue to be linked in low-mass star formation.

Acknowledgements

I would like to first express my sincere gratitude to my mentor Prof. Karin Öberg for her continuous support and guidance throughout my thesis research, and for her patience, motivation, enthusiasm, and substantial knowledge. She was always willing to assist me whenever I ran into difficulties or had questions about either research or writing. Her comments on this thesis were consistently detailed, helpful, and ultimately invaluable for its composition. I would also like to recognize the members of the Öberg Group, whose welcoming nature created a productive and supportive research environment. Specifically, I would like to thank Jenny Bergner, who provided helpful assistance with coding-relating issues during the research process.

I also wish to acknowledge Prof. Michael McCarthy and Dr. David Wilner who served as external readers for this thesis. I am grateful for their detailed and valuable comments, which surely improved the content, clarity, and style of this work.

I would like to thank Prof. David Charbonneau, whose careful organization of the Astronomy 99 course make it possible to undertake this endeavor. His encouragement and regular feedback helped keep me on track throughout both the research and writing phases of this thesis.

Last, but not least, I am grateful for the support of my fellow classmates: Deanna Emery, Ben Lee, Juliana Garcia-Mejia, Andrew Mayo, and Jeremy Dietrich.

Contents

List of Tables	vi
List of Figures	vii
1 Introduction	1
1.1 Low-mass Star Formation	2
1.2 Chemistry in Pre- and Protostellar Environments	3
1.3 Carbon Chain Chemistry	6
1.3.1 Ion-Molecule Chemistry	6
1.3.2 Warm Carbon Chain Chemistry	8
1.4 Outline of the Thesis	11
2 Methods: Observations and Data Analysis	13
2.1 Protostellar Sample	13
2.2 Observational Details and Data Reduction	15
2.3 Molecular Detections	18
2.4 Measuring Integrated Intensities	19
2.5 Column Density Calculations	20
3 Results	27
3.1 Detection Fractions	27
3.2 Carbon Chain Rotational Temperatures	31

3.3	Column Densities and Abundances	34
3.3.1	Column Densities	34
3.3.2	Fractional Abundance Calculation	38
3.4	Sample Statistics	40
3.4.1	Median Column Densities and Abundances	40
3.4.2	Abundance Distributions	42
3.4.3	Correlation Studies	42
4	Discussion	51
4.1	Carbon Chain Chemistry	51
4.1.1	Carbon Chains	52
4.1.2	Nitrogen-Bearing Chains	53
4.1.3	Sulfur-Bearing Chains	54
4.2	Comparison with Cold Clouds	56
4.3	Comparison with Carbon Chain-Rich Protostars	59
5	Conclusions	65
A	Additional Information	67
A.1	Source Descriptions	67
A.1.1	B1-a, B1-c	67
A.1.2	HH 300	68
A.1.3	B5 IRS1	69
A.1.4	L1014 IRS	69
A.1.5	IRAS 23238+7410	71
A.1.6	L1489 IRS	71
A.1.7	IRAS 04108+2803	72
A.1.8	IRAS 03245+3002, L1455 IRS3, L1455 SMM1	72
A.1.9	SVS 4-5	74

A.1.10 L1448 IRS1	74
A.1.11 IRAS 03235+3004, IRAS 03254+3050, IRAS 03271+3013	74
A.2 Complete Spectral Data	75
A.3 Integrated Line Intensities	75
A.4 Rotational Diagrams	75
A.5 Correlation Coefficients and Alternative Column Densities for HC ₅ N	75
Bibliography	90

List of Tables

2.1	Source Information for Protostellar Sample	16
2.2	Characteristic Source Velocities	17
2.3	Rest Frequencies of Observed Transitions	18
3.1	Molecule Line Detections per Source	29
3.2	Summary of Molecular Detections in the 16 Sources	31
3.3	Carbon Chain Rotational Temperatures in K	34
3.4	Carbon Chain Column Densities in cm^{-2}	36
3.5	Median Column Densities and Fractional Abundances	41
3.6	Correlation Coefficients for Molecule Correlations	47
A.1	Integrated Intensities for CS	82
A.2	Integrated Intensities for CCS	83
A.3	Integrated Intensities for CCCS	83
A.4	Integrated Intensities for HC_3N	84
A.5	Integrated Intensities for HC_5N	84
A.6	Integrated Intensities for C_3H	85
A.7	Pearson Correlation Coefficients for Molecule Correlations	88
A.8	Perseus-Only Correlation Coefficients for Molecule Correlations	88
A.9	Column Densities for HC_5N for 13 K	89

List of Figures

1.1	Cartoon of carbon chain chemistry in lukewarm corino	9
2.1	Example Gaussian fits	21
2.2	Synthetic rotational diagrams for CH ₃ CHO	24
2.3	Linear interpolation of CCS partition function	25
2.4	Column density flowchart	26
3.1	Spectral overview of protostellar sample	28
3.2	Labeled IRAM spectra for relevant carbon chains	28
3.3	Zoomed-in CCS spectra	30
3.4	CCS rotational diagrams	32
3.5	Observed column densities	37
3.6	Median column densities and abundances	41
3.7	Column density and abundance distributions	43
3.8	Carbon chain column density correlations between molecules	46
3.9	Column density versus envelope mass	48
3.10	Column density versus bolometric luminosity	50
4.1	Molecular size versus median column density	52
4.2	Fractional abundance compared with cold cloud TMC-1	56
4.3	Abundance ratios compared with cold clouds	58
4.4	Fractional abundance compared with WCCC sources	61

4.5	Column density compared with WCCC sources	62
4.6	Fractional abundances compared with warm-up models	63
A.1	Zoomed-in CS spectra	76
A.2	Zoomed-in CCCS spectra	77
A.3	Zoomed-in HC ₃ N spectra	78
A.4	Zoomed-in C ₃ H spectra	79
A.5	Zoomed-in HC ₅ N spectra	80
A.6	Zoomed-in HC ₅ N spectra (cont.)	81
A.7	Rotational diagrams for CCCS	86
A.8	Rotational diagrams for HC ₃ N	87
A.9	Rotational diagrams for HC ₅ N	88

Chapter 1

Introduction

Astronomical molecules have been detected in diverse environments, spanning nearby objects in the solar system (Crovisier et al., 2004; Mumma and Charnley, 2011; Goesmann et al., 2015) to distant sources in the early universe (Muller et al., 2014). Outside of the solar system (and of extrasolar systems), molecules are primarily associated with cool, dense interstellar and circumstellar material, but they are also found in the hot regions around evolved stars and at lower abundances, in the diffuse interstellar medium. Wherever molecules are detected, they serve as useful probes of the physical conditions of their environments. Information can be derived from both their spectra and underlying chemistry. High-resolution rotational and vibrational spectra yield information about the density and temperature of interstellar gas as well as large-scale motions such as rotation and collapse. Chemical models and simulations, in which molecular abundances are calculated based on their rates of formation and destruction, provide another tool to examine physical conditions. Since molecular abundances are functions of time as well, some abundances can also be used to probe the temporal evolution of different sources (Herbst and van Dishoeck, 2009).

Organic molecules formed at early stages of star formation can become incorporated into protoplanetary disks (Visser et al., 2009, 2011) and further into planetesimals and planets, seeding nascent planets with complex organic material. Molecular abundances around protostars are thus of considerable interest for the study of the origins of life. Low-mass stars

host most planetary systems and so molecular inventories toward low-mass young stellar objects are the most relevant for characterizing potentially habitable environments.

1.1 Low-mass Star Formation

Stars form from cold, dense prestellar globules or cores ($n_H \approx 2 \times 10^4 \text{ cm}^{-3}$, $T \approx 10 \text{ K}$) of sizes 0.1–0.3 pc. These cores are rich in gas-phase molecules and icy mantles of molecules atop dust particles (Herbst and van Dishoeck, 2009). The dust particles themselves are thought to be composed of silicates and carbonaceous matter, with sizes ranging from 10 nm to $0.5 \mu\text{m}$ (Jones, 2016). The dust grains and their icy mantles are major reservoirs for heavy elements. The first step in star formation is the collapse of these cold cores due to their own self-gravity. This collapse is initially isothermal as atoms and molecules release energy in the form of radiation as the collapse proceeds (Bergin and Tafalla, 2007). Once a condensation of sufficient density ($n_H \sim 10^{5-7} \text{ cm}^{-3}$) and radius ($r \approx 0.02\text{--}0.05 \text{ pc}$) is formed, it becomes opaque, starts to heat up as further collapse occurs, and emits a continuum of infrared radiation. The resulting young stellar object (YSO) encompasses a variety of phenomena including: *a*) outflows, consisting of jets and shocks (Snell et al., 1980; Lada, 1985; Arce and Sargent, 2005; Hirano et al., 2006), *b*) warm inner envelopes passively heated by the protostars with typical temperatures of $\approx 100 \text{ K}$ and densities of 10^{7-8} cm^{-3} (Adams et al., 1987; Shirley et al., 2000; Jørgensen et al., 2002; Robitaille et al., 2006), and *c*) nascent protoplanetary disks (Sargent and Beckwith, 1987; Strom et al., 1989; O’dell and Wen, 1994). These inner envelopes, when associated with complex organic molecule emission, are known as hot corinos (Ceccarelli, 2005), which are the low-mass analogs of hot cores (Kurtz et al., 2000). These hot corinos, which are of undetermined geometry, have sizes of about 100 AU or less (Ceccarelli, 2005), which is similar in size to a typical protoplanetary disk. There is also evidence for protostellar sources in which the bulk of the envelope is only

partially heated to temperatures well below 100 K, which are known as lukewarm corinos (Hassel et al., 2008). Eventually, much of the matter is blown away, and the young stellar object begins life as a T Tauri star surrounded by a dense protoplanetary disk.

1.2 Chemistry in Pre- and Protostellar Environments

The study of interstellar molecules has helped to elucidate the evolutionary stages of star formation in the Milky Way, especially for low-mass stars with luminosities $\lesssim 10^2 L_{\odot}$. Molecular spectroscopy is able to probe the diverse temperature, distance, and density scales involved in star formation. Molecules provide a direct measure of velocity fields within cloud cores and their abundances constrain the internal and external stellar radiation fields. A significant fraction of molecules is condensed in icy mantles of dust grains, which yield important information on the temperature and irradiation history of the region. Since chemistry controls the critical physical parameters in star formation such as fractional ionization and cooling of the gas, a detailed understanding of the chemical composition of gas and dust surrounding young stars is necessary for understanding stellar formation and evolution (van Dishoeck and Blake, 1998). Understanding the chemistry in prestellar and protostellar cores is also important to predict the chemical composition of planets forming at later stages. In this context, the abundances of different types of organic molecules are especially informative.

Currently, about 150 different molecules have been detected, mainly via rotational emission spectra obtained from ground and space-based millimeter-wave telescopes (Markwick-Kemper, 2003; Neufeld et al., 2015; Jørgensen et al., 2016). The majority of these molecules, compared to the standards of terrestrial organic chemistry, are not large, ranging in size from 2 to 13 atoms, with some notable exceptions (e.g. fullerenes; Cami et al., 2010). Despite being the dominant molecule in all dense sources, H_2 is difficult to detect. It can be observed, although with some difficulty, in infrared vibrational absorption in cool, dense sources, in UV

absorption through diffuse matter, and via rotational and vibrational emission in warm or shocked matter (e.g. Allers et al., 2005; Likkell et al., 2006; Nisini et al., 2010; Appleton et al., 2017). Other gas-phase molecules only represent minor constituents of the gas. The second most abundant gaseous molecule, carbon monoxide (CO), has typical fractional abundances of 10^{-4} of that of molecular hydrogen in dense objects. Larger species range in fractional abundances down to 10^{-11} with respect to H_2 .

While many of the detected molecules are commonly found on Earth, others are exotic by terrestrial standards. These exotic molecules include: molecular ions of both positive (e.g. HCO^+) and negative (e.g. C_4H^-) charge; radicals with unpaired electrons (e.g. C_6H); and unstable isomers (e.g. HCN and HNC) with the same atomic constituents but different structures (Herbst and van Dishoeck, 2009). Isotopologues containing rare isotopes such as deuterium, ^{13}C , ^{15}N , ^{17}O , ^{18}O , and ^{34}S have also been observed (Herbst and van Dishoeck, 2009).

Molecules in the solid phase have been detected, primarily via broad absorption spectra (Whittet, 2003). Relative to their gas-phase analogs, molecules detected on grain surfaces are smaller in size, because the absorption features from complex species are weaker and lack specificity (Gibb et al., 2000). The most abundant such molecule in cold sources is water ice, which has typical fractional abundances with respect to H_2 of about 10^{-4} , comparable to gas-phase CO (Boogert, 2016). Somewhat lower abundances have been reported for solid-phase carbon dioxide (CO_2) and CO (Herbst and van Dishoeck, 2009). Methane (CH_4) and methanol (CH_3OH), key starting points for forming larger organic molecules, are also important ice constituents with median abundances of $\sim 5 \times 10^{-6}$ for both (Öberg et al., 2008, 2011a; Boogert, 2016).

The majority of known interstellar and circumstellar molecules are organic as they contain carbon. In fact, for species containing six or more atoms, 100% of the molecules are organic.

Hydrogen-rich organics with six atoms or more are referred to as complex organic molecules (COMs) (Herbst and van Dishoeck, 2009). There is also a second class of large organic molecules in the form of unsaturated carbon chains. The term unsaturated refers to molecules that have few hydrogen atoms, such as the carbon chains (C_n ; $n = 2, 3, 5$), the radicals of the form C_nH ($n = 2-8$), and the cyanopolyynes (HC_nN ; $n = 3, 5, 7, 9, 11$), whereas the term saturated refers to organics richer in hydrogen, such as dimethyl ether (CH_3OCH_3). In strict chemical terms, saturated molecules are limited to single bonds between valence electrons; most organic molecules of terrestrial origin are saturated or near-saturated (Herbst and van Dishoeck, 2009). Both kinds of molecules will contribute to the organic budget in the later, planet-forming stage of star formation. The more well-studied COMs are discussed briefly below, followed by a detailed introduction of carbon chain chemistry, which is the main focus of this thesis.

Complex organic molecules were initially observed in hot cores toward high-mass protostars (Blake et al., 1987). Over the past two decades, COMs have been shown to be abundant in many other circumstellar and interstellar environments, including pre-stellar cores, protostellar envelopes, outflows, and hot cores in low-mass star-forming regions (e.g. Cazaux et al., 2003; Bottinelli et al., 2004, 2007; Arce et al., 2008; Öberg et al., 2011b). COMs have also been observed toward cold cloud cores, the traditional sites of carbon chains (Öberg et al., 2010; Bacmann et al., 2012; Cernicharo et al., 2012). These detections suggest that there are several robust formation pathways for COMs and that COMs may be common during the formation of low-mass or solar-mass stars. Based on experiments and models, COMs form efficiently on grain surfaces through energetic processing of simple ices and are released into the gas phase via thermal or nonthermal processes (Garrod and Herbst, 2006; Garrod et al., 2008; Öberg et al., 2009). For a more detailed description of grain surface chemistry, see the review by Herbst and van Dishoeck (2009). Recent theoretical work has

shown that COMs may also be formed in the gas phase following the desorption of methanol (Balucani et al., 2015).

1.3 Carbon Chain Chemistry

1.3.1 Ion-Molecule Chemistry

Carbon chain molecules were first observed in the cold, dark cloud TMC-1 in the form of cyanopolynes (Little et al., 1977; Broten et al., 1978; Kroto et al., 1978). Ever since, carbon chain molecules have typically been associated with the cold, dark cloud stage of star formation (Suzuki et al., 1992; Markwick et al., 2000; Hirota et al., 2004; Smith et al., 2004). In this environment, carbon chains form through efficient low-temperature ion-molecule reactions in the gas phase (Herbst and Leung, 1989; Ohishi and Kaifu, 1998). Once H_2 , which is formed on the surfaces of dust particles (Gould and Salpeter, 1963), is ejected into the gas, complex species form via gas-phase chemistry. At the low temperatures in cold, dense cores ($T_{\text{gas}} \approx T_{\text{grain}} \approx 10 \text{ K}$), the chemistry is dominated by exothermic reactions which have no potential barriers between reactants and products (Herbst and van Dishoeck, 2009). Reactions involving positive ions and neutrals (ion-neutral reactions) typically satisfy this criterion and thus predominate in these conditions (Herbst and Klemperer, 1973; Watson, 1973). In dense regions, positive ions are formed mainly via cosmic ray (CR) bombardment and subsequent reactions. The simplest polyatomic ion H_3^+ , which is an essential ingredient of cold carbon chain chemistry, is formed in such a process:

A similar pathway, which transforms relatively inert CO into chemically active C^+ , begins with the ionization of He (Indriolo et al., 2009):

A substantial amount of ionization is due to secondary electrons relaxing back to thermal conditions (Cravens and Dalgarno, 1978). In addition to ionization, cosmic rays result in the internal production of UV photons via a mechanism in which secondary electrons excite H_2 , which then reradiates back to the ground electronic state (Prasad and Tarafdar, 1983; Gredel et al., 1989). Since they are able to photodissociate and photoionize many species, even in high visual extinction environments, these photons are an important source of molecular destruction (Herbst and van Dishoeck, 2009).

Chains of ion-molecule reactions beginning with H_3^+ and other primeval atomic species lead to a variety of complex molecular ions. However, these ions are typically unsaturated as “H-atom transfer” reactions involving molecular ions (X^+) of the type

which serve as the main chemical process for hydrogenation, are either endothermic or possess potential barriers, prohibiting them from occurring at low temperatures (Herbst and van Dishoeck, 2009). For instance, H-atom transfer reactions cannot produce ions with $m > 2$ for hydrocarbon ions C_nH_m^+ for $n > 3$ (McEwan et al., 1999). Additionally, once positive molecular ions are formed, dissociative recombination processes such as

tend to produce neutral fragments that contain one or more hydrogen atoms fewer than the ionic structure. While there are some radiative association reactions between ions and H_2 which produce more saturated ions (Bates, 1987), the net result is that complex molecules formed in gas-phase chemical models of cold sources tend to be very unsaturated. Moreover, the fact that ion-molecule reactions involving C^+ or C and neutral-neutral reactions with C

lead to carbon insertion at low temperatures, this chemistry tends to produce long carbon chains (Herbst and van Dishoeck, 2009). Ion-molecule pathways from H_3^+ , C, and C^+ to neutrals as complex as C_6H are shown in Smith (1992). Herbst and Millar (2008) have reviewed ion-molecule chemistry in cold cores in some detail.

In some dark cores, long unsaturated carbon chains such as HC_5N have orders-of-magnitude higher abundance ratios with respect to saturated molecules such as CH_3OH . Among cold cores, and even within a single cold core, the abundances of long chains can vary by more than a factor of 10, indicating that their chemistry is tied to special conditions or specific timescales. By contrast, in hot cores, saturated molecules are more abundant than unsaturated carbon chains (Herbst and van Dishoeck, 2009). This observation is explained by a combination of the efficient destruction of carbon chains in dense and hot environments, as well as the rapid release of COMs into the gas phase when icy grain mantles sublimate.

1.3.2 Warm Carbon Chain Chemistry

It has been traditionally assumed that the observed low abundances of carbon chain molecules seen in star-forming regions were due to chemical evolutionary stage (Hirahara et al., 1992; Herbst and van Dishoeck, 2009). By the time a protostar reaches the hot core/corino phase, a large fraction of the carbon atoms have already been fixed as CO and the carbon chain molecules cannot be efficiently produced due to a deficit of carbon atoms. Moreover, many carbon chain molecules produced in the early, cold core stages have been lost by reactions with He^+ , H^+ , and H_3^+ in typical timescales of 10^6 yr (Suzuki et al., 1992) as well as via depletion onto dust grains (Hassel et al., 2008).

In 2008, Sakai et al. detected evidence of gaseous carbon chain species (e.g. C_nH , HC_{2n+1}N) in the lukewarm ($T \approx 30$ K) corino of low-mass protostar L1527. Detections toward a second source in the following year (Sakai et al., 2009) suggested that carbon

chains may be common toward some classes of protostars. The term “warm carbon chain chemistry” (WCCC) was coined to describe this new type of source. Low-temperature modeling of ion-molecule chemistry and chemical inheritance underpredicts the high carbon chain abundances seen in these WCCC sources. To account for this discrepancy, Sakai et al. (2008) proposed that carbon chains can also be formed in lukewarm protostellar envelopes when methane, a common interstellar ice, sublimates at 25 K (Öberg et al., 2008). This sublimation temperature is higher than that of CO (~ 20 K) but is significantly lower than that of H₂O (~ 100 K). Hence, CH₄ can be abundant in a warm region which is somewhat extended

Figure 1.1: Cartoon representation explaining the excess carbon chains observed in a lukewarm corino. There are two primary routes for carbon chain production: *i*) Surviving carbon chains are inherited from the cold cloud phase, when they are efficiently produced via ion-molecule phase-gas chemistry when $T_{\text{gas}} \approx T_{\text{grain}} \approx 10$ K. *ii*) Carbon chains can also be produced via warm carbon chain chemistry, driven by the sublimation of CH₄-rich dust grains and gas-phase interactions with C⁺. The grains, which are typically 0.1 μm , are not drawn to scale. The collapsing envelope is typically of size ~ 0.05 pc and the corino is about $\lesssim 100$ AU.

around the protostar (Hassel et al., 2008). In the gas phase, CH_4 then reacts with C^+ to efficiently form carbon chains in the dense region heated by the emerging protostar (see Hassel et al. (2008) for a detailed description of the intermediary reactions responsible for carbon chain production). This WCCC theory, which is summarized in Figure 1.1, has since been validated by chemical models (Hassel et al., 2011; Aikawa et al., 2012).

The new production pathway suggested by Sakai et al. (2008, 2009) also yields predictions about the temporal evolution of a cold cloud core. If the starless core phase is short, the bulk of the carbonaceous ice forms from accretion of C atoms. The carbon atoms are then hydrogenated to form CH_4 and the release of CH_4 during protostellar formation promotes WCCC. However, if the starless core phase is long-lived, most of the gas-phase carbon atoms have sufficient time to react and form CO, resulting in CO-dominated ice. CH_3OH , which forms through CO hydrogenation, is the starting point of COM chemistry on grain surfaces (Sakai and Yamamoto, 2013).

Four WCCC sources have been identified and they include: L1527 (Sakai et al., 2008), B228 (Sakai et al., 2009), TMC-1A (Aso et al., 2015), and L483 (Oya et al., 2017). Although these anomalous sources have been well-studied, the typical carbon chain chemistry presented by low-mass protostars remains largely unconstrained.

1.4 Outline of the Thesis

The goal of this thesis is to determine the typical carbon chain chemistry found in low-mass protostars and to elucidate the origins of the observed molecules. Abundance variations among carbon chain families and protostellar sources will yield valuable information on this underlying chemistry, helping to clarify the roles of WCCC and chemical inheritance. Such a comparison may also shed light on the poorly understood and infrequently observed sulfur-bearing carbon chains, a family of molecules previously shown to correlate strongly with carbon chain chemistry in cold clouds. With these motivations, we present the result of a

carbon chain survey toward a unbiased sample of 16 embedded solar-type protostars using the IRAM 30 m telescope. In this thesis, we seek to understand the typical carbon chain composition for a solar-type protostar at the icy envelope stage. We also aim to characterize relationships among different classes of carbon chain molecules as well as the physical and chemical properties of protostars exhibiting excess carbon chains.

This thesis is organized as follows:

In Chapter 2, we discuss our protostellar sample, the observational details, and the process of data reduction. The procedure for identifying molecular detections and constraining upper limits is described along with the Gaussian fitting techniques used to measure the integrated intensities of detected rotational spectral lines. The theory underpinning the use of rotational diagrams, excitation temperature determinations, and column density calculations is also presented.

In Chapter 3, we present an overview of the spectral line data. We determine the column densities, and where possible, rotational temperatures of detected carbon chains. We then use these results to obtain an estimate of the frequency distribution of carbon chains toward low-mass YSOs. We also investigate correlations between different carbon chain species and derive median values for carbon chain abundances from this sample using survival analysis.

In Chapter 4, we comment on the implications for carbon chain formation chemistry based on our findings. We also compare our results with previous studies of different classes of objects, including cold cloud cores and lukewarm protostellar envelopes, together with model predictions to explore whether inheritance or in situ production is more likely.

In Chapter 5, we summarize our conclusions.

Chapter 2

Methods: Observations and Data Analysis

This work represents the third study focused on this low-mass protostellar sample (Graninger et al., 2016; Bergner et al., submitted). Graninger et al. (2016) report a positive correlation between C₄H and methanol in these protostars, while Bergner et al. (submitted) present an overview of observed COMs. The analysis methods in this thesis are adopted from these previous works and are especially influenced by Bergner et al. (submitted).

2.1 Protostellar Sample

The sample consists of 16 low-mass protostars in the nearby star-forming regions Perseus, Taurus, and Serpens as well as a number of isolated cores. The sample and selection criteria are presented in detail in Graninger et al. (2016). Here we briefly summarize the sample data most relevant for this thesis. Sources were selected from the *Spitzer c2d* ice sample presented in Boogert et al. (2008). The ice sample represents a subset of the spectral surveys of nearby molecular clouds and isolated dense cores in the context of the *Spitzer* Legacy Program “From Molecular Cores to Planet-Forming Disks” (*c2d*; Evans et al., 2003) which exhibited conspicuous ice absorption features. The presence and nature of excess IR emission, as measured by the spectral index α_{IR} , in the spectral energy distributions (SEDs) of YSOs

roughly indicate their evolutionary stage. Younger objects exhibit substantial IR excess due to the presence of their circumstellar envelopes. As the YSOs age, IR flux decreases as their envelopes dissipate and their protoplanetary disks transition to debris disks. The sources are characterized into classes according to their SEDs based on α_{IR} , which is defined as the slope between 2 and 24 μm , i.e.

$$\alpha_{\text{IR}} = \frac{d \log(\lambda F_{\lambda})}{d \log \lambda}. \quad (2.1)$$

Source selection was constrained to northern hemisphere sources, as these are easily observable with the IRAM 30 m telescope. Additionally, only Class 0/I sources were considered, which in terms of spectral index, is defined by $\alpha_{\text{IR}} > 0.3$ (Wilking et al., 2001). Since Class 0/I objects are frequently, but not exclusively, associated with deeply embedded protostars, a further selection cut was made to include only those sources with a firm protostellar association. Potential confusion can arise as edge-on disks can appear similar to protostars in terms of their SEDs. In total, 16 sources were chosen and their parameters are shown in Table 2.1.

A majority of the sources reside in the Perseus molecular cloud, a moderately clustered star-forming region that is more complicated than the quiescent, low-mass Taurus molecular cloud but less so than the turbulent Orion molecular cloud currently forming high-mass stars (Ladd et al., 1993, 1994; Kirk et al., 2007). Distance estimates ranging from 220 to 315 pc indicate a relatively nearby cloud and owing to this large spread in distance scale, have also prompted several authors to suggest that Perseus may be composed of more than one cloud (e.g. Cernicharo, 1991; Cernis, 1993; Luhman et al., 2003). Perseus represents an ideal environment for studying the formation of low-mass stars characterized by moderate levels of clustering and turbulence.

The other sources are drawn from the well-known star-forming regions of Serpens and Taurus (e.g. Ortiz-León et al., 2015; Dzib et al., 2015; Guilloteau et al., 2016) and isolated

cores such as CB244 and L1014 (e.g. Huard et al., 2006; Stutz et al., 2010). The inclusion of objects from diverse regions with varied physical environments complements the subsample of sources from Perseus. Having a diverse set of sources makes it possible to investigate correlations between the physical conditions around protostars and the nature of carbon chain chemistry that is observed.

If we assume a distance of 250 pc to Perseus as reported in Schlafly et al. (2014), Class 0/I objects, which have diameters of ~ 10000 AU (Bergin and Tafalla, 2007), located in the cloud will have typical angular scales of $\sim 40''$. The sources shown in Table 2.1 have envelope masses ($0.1\text{--}17.7 M_{\odot}$) and bolometric luminosities ($0.32\text{--}17.0 L_{\odot}$) which span several orders of magnitude. The luminosity of the protostar will set the thermal structure, while the envelope masses allow us to estimate the amount of material present around each protostar. Water ice column densities, which provide an additional tracer of circumstellar material, also vary between $\sim 0.5\text{--}40 \times 10^{18} \text{ cm}^{-2}$. The diversity of intrinsic source parameters allows for the determination of potential correlations between molecular detections/line strengths and physical protostar characteristics.

2.2 Observational Details and Data Reduction

Detailed information about the observational setup can be found in Graninger et al. (2016). Here we briefly describe the setup and observational configuration. All sources were observed with the IRAM 30 m telescope using the EMIR 90 GHz receiver and the Fourier Transform Spectrometer (FTS) backend, which contains two 8 GHz sidebands with an 8 GHz gap in-between. Six of the sources (B1-a, B5 IRS1, L1489 IRS, IRAS 04108+2803, IRAS 03235+3004, and SVS 4-5) were observed on June 12–16, 2013 at 93–101 GHz and 109–117 GHz. The remaining sources were observed on July 23–28, 2014 at 92–100 GHz and 108–116 GHz. The spectral resolution for both sets of observations was 200 kHz and

Table 2.1: Source Information of the Complete 16-object *c2d* Embedded Protostar Sample with Ice Detections

Source	R.A. (J2000.0)	Dec (J2000.0)	Cloud	L_{bol} (L_{\odot})	M_{env} (M_{\odot})	α_{IR}^a	$N(\text{H}_2\text{O})^a$ 10^{18} cm^{-2}
B1-a ^b	03:33:16.67	31:07:55.1	Perseus	1.3 ^c	2.8 ^c	1.87	10.39 ± 2.26
SVS 4-5 ^b	18:29:57.59	01:13:00.6	Serpens	38 ^g	—	1.26	5.65 ± 1.13
B1-c	03:33:17.89	31:09:31.0	Perseus	3.7 ^c	17.7 ^c	2.66	29.55 ± 5.65
IRAS 23238+7401	23:25:46.65	74:17:37.2	CB244	—	—	0.95	12.95 ± 2.26
L1455 IRS3	03:28:00.41	30:08:01.2	Perseus	0.32 ^c	0.2 ^e	0.98	0.92 ± 0.37
B5 IRS 1 ^b	03:47:41.61	32:51:43.8	Perseus	4.7 ^c	4.2 ^c	0.78	2.26 ± 0.28
L1455 SMM1	03:27:43.25	30:12:28.8	Perseus	3.1 ^c	5.3 ^c	2.41	18.21 ± 2.82
IRAS 03245+3002	03:27:39.03	30:12:59.3	Perseus	7.0 ^c	5.3 ^c	2.70	39.31 ± 5.65
L1014 IRS	21:24:07.51	49:59:09.0	L1014	—	—	1.28	7.16 ± 0.91
IRAS 04108+2803 ^b	04:13:54.72	28:11:32.9	Taurus	0.62 ^d	—	0.90	2.87 ± 0.40
IRAS 03235+3004 ^b	03:26:37.45	30:15:27.9	Perseus	1.9 ^c	2.4 ^c	1.44	14.48 ± 2.26
L1489 IRS ^b	04:04:43.07	26:18:56.4	Taurus	3.7 ^d	0.1 ^f	1.10	4.26 ± 0.51
HH 300	04:26:56.30	24:43:35.3	Taurus	1.27 ^d	—	0.79	2.59 ± 0.25
IRAS 03271+3013	03:30:15.16	30:23:48.8	Perseus	0.8 ^c	1.2 ^c	2.06	7.69 ± 1.76
IRAS 03254+3050	03:28:34.51	31:00:51.2	Perseus	—	0.3 ^c	0.90	3.66 ± 0.47
L1448 IRS1	03:25:09.44	30:46:21.7	Perseus	17.0 ^c	16.3 ^c	0.34	0.47 ± 0.16

Note: Adapted from Graninger et al. (2016).

^aBoogert et al. (2008).

^bSources were observed by Öberg et al. (2014).

^cHatchell et al. (2007).

^dFurlan et al. (2008).

^eEnoch et al. (2009).

^fBrinch et al. (2007).

^gPontoppidan et al. (2004).

the sideband rejection was -15 dB (Carter et al., 2012).

Pointing accuracy was checked every 1–2 hr and was determined to be within $2''$ – $3''$. Focus was checked every 4 hr and remained stable. The telescope beam size ranges from $27''$ at 92 GHz to $21''$ at 117 GHz. For this range of frequencies, the pointing accuracy is always substantially smaller than the beamsize ($< 15\%$). Excluding the highest frequency spectral window, the rms values range from 2–7 mK as reported by Bergner et al. (submitted).

The CLASS¹ software package was used to reduce the spectra. The software is designed

¹<http://www.iram.fr/IRAMFR/GILDAS>

for reducing spectroscopic data obtained on a single-dish telescope and is the principle software used to reduce all data acquired with the IRAM 30 m telescope.

The spectra, taken from Bergner et al. (submitted), were fit with a global baseline to each 4 GHz spectral chunk using four to seven line-free windows. Individual scans were baseline subtracted and averaged. Then, using CLASS, the beam efficiency was modified using Ruze’s equation with scaling factor 0.861 and sigma of 63.6 microns, resulting in beam efficiencies at the first, middle, and last channel of 0.8106, 0.7975, and 0.7830. The scaling factor and sigma value are the same as used in Bergner et al. (submitted). With a forward efficiency of 0.95, the antenna temperature, T_a^* , was converted to main beam temperature, T_{mb} . Literature source velocities were initially used to convert spectra to an approximate rest frequency. Fine-tuning adjustments were then made using CS $J = 2 - 1$ transitions. The assumed characteristic velocities for each source are shown in Table 2.2.

Table 2.2: Characteristic Source Velocities

Source	V_0 (km/s)
B1-a	6.4
SVS 4-5	7.9
B1-c	6.5
IRAS 23238+7401	4.5
L1455 IRS3	5.0
B5 IRS 1	10.1
L1455 SMM1	5.1
IRAS 03245+3002	5.0
L1014 IRS	4.4
IRAS 04108+2803	7.2
IRAS 03235+3004	5.5
L1489 IRS	7.7
HH 300	7.0
IRAS 03271+3013	5.5
IRAS 03254+3050	7.2
L1448 IRS1	3.4

2.3 Molecular Detections

A number of carbon chain molecules are covered by our spectral setting: CCS, CCCS, HC₃N, HC₅N, C₃H, and C₄H. We also include CS in our analysis to constrain the sulfur carbon chain chemistry. The frequencies, line strengths, and upper-state energies of the observed lines are summarized in Table 2.3.

Table 2.3: Rest Frequencies of the Observed Transitions

Molecule	Transition	ν (MHz)	S^a	E_u (K)
CS	$J = 2 - 1$	96412.950	2.00	6.25
	$J = 2 - 1$	97172.064	7.98	6.31
	$J = 2 - 1$	97980.953	2.00	7.05
CCS	$J_N = 8_7 - 7_6$	93870.107	7.97	19.89
	$J_N = 7_8 - 6_7$	99866.521	6.87	28.14
	$J_N = 8_9 - 7_8$	113410.186	7.89	33.58
CCCS	$J = 17 - 16$	98268.518	17.00	42.45
	$J = 19 - 18$	109828.293	19.00	52.71
HC ₃ N	$J = 11 - 10$	100076.392	11.00	28.82
	$J = 12 - 11$	109173.634	12.00	34.06
HC ₅ N	$J = 35 - 34$	93188.471	34.99	80.50
	$J = 36 - 35$	95850.714	35.99	85.10
	$J = 37 - 36$	98512.933	36.99	89.83
	$J = 41 - 40$	109161.555	40.99	110.02
	$J = 42 - 41$	111823.643	41.99	115.39
C ₃ H	$J = 43 - 42$	114485.704	42.99	120.88
	$J_{F,l=e} = \left(\frac{9}{2}\right)_5 - \left(\frac{7}{2}\right)_4$	97995.166	4.89	12.54
	$J_{F,l=e} = \left(\frac{9}{2}\right)_4 - \left(\frac{7}{2}\right)_3$	97995.913	3.89	12.54
	$J_{F,l=f} = \left(\frac{9}{2}\right)_5 - \left(\frac{7}{2}\right)_4$	98011.611	4.87	12.54
	$J_{F,l=f} = \left(\frac{9}{2}\right)_4 - \left(\frac{7}{2}\right)_3$	98012.524	3.87	12.54
C ₄ H ^b	$N_F = 10_{11} - 9_{10}$	95150.397	10.23	25.11
	$N_F = 10_9 - 9_8$	95188.946	8.36	25.13
	$N_F = 12_{12} - 11_{11}$	114182.512	11.17	35.62
	$N_F = 12_{11} - 11_{10}$	114221.040	10.23	35.64

^a Line strength.

^b C₄H transitions were reported in Graninger et al. (2016).

A molecule is considered to be detected provided that (1) at least one line with a 5σ detection or two lines with 3σ detections are observed, (2) there is no confusion with common interstellar or YSO molecular lines, and (3) non-detected lines have upper limits that are consistent with the populations predicted by detected lines. The treatment of upper limits is discussed in Section 2.5 in more detail. Since even the line-rich sources in our survey are line-poor in comparison to hot cores, overlapping lines are generally not a concern, and a single line is sufficient to claim a detection when there are no competing line identifications. These detection criteria are identical to those adopted in Bergner et al. (submitted).

Line candidates within the observed frequency range were identified using the JPL² and CDMS³ catalogs. Detected lines typically had upper excitation energies less than 150 K, consistent with the fact that the envelopes of most protostars have typical temperatures of ~ 20 –100 K. The data from the catalogs were accessed using the Splatologue⁴ web interface.

2.4 Measuring Integrated Intensities

Integrated intensities for each observed line were determined by fitting single Gaussians to each feature. The integrated intensity, $\int T_{\text{mb}} dV$, which is determined by integrating the main beam temperature T_{mb} over the relevant velocity dV range that corresponds to the fitted Gaussian profile. Based on our data, a Gaussian fit is a reasonable assumption for the intrinsic line shape. We assume that the noise is Gaussian in nature and disregard substructure (e.g. as from other sources, such as outflows within in the beam or perturbations in the protostar itself) that cannot be attributed to spectroscopic multiplets.

Representative fits for the $J_N = 8_7 - 7_6$ transition of CCS are shown in Figure 2.1. The left panel illustrates a well-fitting Gaussian profile for source B1-a that is free from

²<http://spec.jpl.nasa.gov>

³<http://www.astro.uni-koeln.de/cdms/catalog>

⁴<http://www.cv.nrao.edu/php/splat/>

complicating noise substructure, while the right panel demonstrates the challenges of fitting spectral features close to significant substructure, likely due to emission from a protostellar outflow, for source IRAS 03271. In the process of line fitting, contributions from outflows are actively excluded. If the outflow emission was also fitted, this would lead to spurious enhancements in the measured molecular line intensities. The chemical processes in outflows are also likely to be very different from those occurring in the protostellar core and envelope (Tafalla and Bachiller, 2011), making chemical abundance comparisons uninformative.

Figure 2.1: Gaussian fits of the CCS $J_N = 8_7 - 7_6$ transition at 93.870 GHz for two sources. Left) The Gaussian fit for B1-a characterizes the line shape well and no prominent noise substructure is present around the feature. Right) Substantial substructure is seen toward higher frequencies around the feature in IRAS 03271+3013. A Gaussian profile is only able to capture one portion of the spectral feature and the remaining substructure is excluded.

For lines with spectroscopic multiplets, only the central peak was used in determining column densities. Unresolved multiplets originating from the same species were treated as a single line by combining the degeneracies and line intensities. Overlapping lines with contributions from different species were excluded from further analysis. In addition to the uncertainty in the line fit, we assume a calibration uncertainty of 10%.

A few protostars including IRAS 03254+3050 and B1-c displayed moderate self-absorption

in strong lines such as CS. Graninger et al. (2016) previously identified IRAS 03254+3050 as exhibiting significant self-absorption in their study of C₄H and CH₃OH and excluded the protostar from their analysis. As the self-absorption only occurs in the strongest lines and sources, we decide to include these sources in our analysis with the caveat that the derived column densities for sources exhibiting self-absorption represent underestimates of the true column densities.

2.5 Column Density Calculations

For molecules with multiple line detections spread over a range of energies, we use rotational diagrams to calculate column densities (Goldsmith and Langer, 1999). Upper level populations for each line are calculated by:

$$\frac{N_u}{g_u} = \frac{3k_B \int T_{\text{mb}} dV}{8\pi^3 \nu \mu^2 S} \quad (2.2)$$

where g_u is the statistical weight of level u , k_B is the Boltzmann constant, ν is the transition frequency, μ is the permanent dipole moment, S is the intrinsic line strength, and N_u is the column density in the upper level u . Assuming optically thin lines and local thermodynamic equilibrium (LTE), each molecule's total column density, N_{tot} , and rotational temperature, T_{rot} , in each source can be determined from:

$$\frac{N_u}{g_u} = \frac{N_{\text{tot}}}{Q(T_{\text{rot}})} \exp\left(-\frac{E_u}{T_{\text{rot}}}\right) \quad (2.3)$$

where $Q(T_{\text{rot}})$ is the rotational partition function and E_u is the energy of the upper level u (Goldsmith and Langer, 1999). We assume that the sources are homogeneous, fill the telescope beam, and that all molecules within the beam can be described by a single temperature (Bisschop et al., 2007a; Öberg et al., 2014; Fayolle et al., 2015). Even though this last assumption will generally be incorrect, the rotational diagram method gives the average

excitation temperature of the region from which most of the molecular emission arises. If the lines are sub-thermally excited because the density is below the critical density, the rotational temperature is a lower limit and this may explain some of the scatter we see in rotational diagrams (Bisschop et al., 2007b). Although the sources are unlikely to be uniform, we make the assumption of homogeneity as we lack spatially-resolved observations and do not know the true spatial distributions. For some molecules, the sources will not fill the telescope beam, but without prior knowledge about the emission distribution, we cannot calculate an accurate beam-filling factor and therefore, choose to report data without any beam-dilution factor applied.

Rotational diagrams are typically presented with logarithmic y-scales since a plot of the logarithm of the right-hand side of Equation 2.3 as a function of E_u results in a straight line with slope $-1/T_{\text{rot}}$ and intercept $N_{\text{tot}}/Q(T_{\text{rot}})$. Explicitly, we can rewrite Equation 2.3 to demonstrate this:

$$\ln \left(\frac{N_u}{g_u} \right) = \ln N_{\text{tot}} - \ln Q(T_{\text{rot}}) - \frac{E_u}{T_{\text{rot}}}. \quad (2.4)$$

A synthetic rotational diagram for CH_3CHO is shown in Figure 2.2. In the left panel, the effect of fitting different linear slopes on rotational temperature is evident. Relative to the actual fit (shown in black), slopes which are more steeply negative result in lower rotational temperatures (shown in red) while more gradual slopes produce higher temperatures (shown in blue). As illustrated in the right panel, column density depends on the y-intercept of the linear fit. Compared to the actual fit, larger intercept values result in greater column density predictions and smaller intercepts predict smaller column densities.

For diatomic molecules and linear rotors, the intrinsic molecular parameters are dipole moment $S(J) = J$ and partition function $Q(T) = k_B T/hB$ in the high-temperature limit ($hB \ll k_B T$) with rotational constant $B = h/8\pi^2 I$, where I is the moment of inertia and h

Figure 2.2: Synthetic rotational diagrams for CH_3CHO . Black circles indicate detections with associated uncertainties. Dashed lines represent fits to the data. The black line shows the actual fit and the red and blue show the exaggerated impact of different fits on rotation temperature (left) and column density (right). For this molecule, uncertainties, estimated from the uncertainties of the fitting parameters, on the rotation temperature and column density are on the order of ~ 1 K and $0.4 \times 10^{12} \text{ cm}^{-2}$, respectively. Data for the rotation diagrams were taken from Öberg et al. (2014) for protostar B1-a.

is the Planck constant. For nonlinear molecules, the formulas for S and Q become more complex (Townes and Schawlow, 1955). The above equation assumes that the vibrational partition function can be set to unity, but for large molecules, this assumption can break down even at temperatures of 100–200 K (Herbst and van Dishoeck, 2009).

In practice, due to the complexity of the formulas for the rotational partition functions of large molecules, linear interpolation of empirical values is used. The empirical values for the partition function were taken from the CDMS/JPL databases, using a consistent choice for the partition function and S values. An example of a linear interpolation for the partition function of CCS is shown in Figure 2.3. The high R^2 value obtained indicates that linear interpolation is an excellent fit to the empirical data, especially considering we are primarily concerned with the low temperature regime (~ 5 –100 K) where the density of measured

empirical partition function values is the greatest, reducing the potential for introducing error.

Figure 2.3: Linear interpolation of the partition function of CCS. The empirical data points are shown as black circles and are taken from the CDMS catalog. The linear interpolation used to calculate column density is shown as a dotted line.

3σ line intensity upper limits were calculated according to:

$$\sigma = \text{rms} \times \text{FWHM} / \sqrt{n_{\text{ch}}}. \quad (2.5)$$

Here, the rms is taken from a 40 km s^{-1} spectral window containing the transition. The FWHM was taken to be the same as that of other lines of the same molecule, if such lines exist, or of closely related molecules in the same source. n_{ch} is the number of channels across the FWHM, which, in this case, is equal to $\sim \text{FWHM} / 0.6 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ channel}^{-1}$. Equation 2.2 is then used to calculate the population upper limits.

For each source, in cases where only a single transition of an individual molecule was detected, the column densities were calculated adopting the average rotational temperatures

for that molecule across the sample. Column density upper limits were also calculated using the sample-averaged rotational temperatures. For sources containing outlier temperatures for a particular molecule, the median rotational temperature was used in place of the average. Figure 2.4 shows a schematic flowchart detailing the process used to derive column densities from detected molecular transitions.

Figure 2.4: Flowchart detailing the procedure used to derive column densities via the number of observed molecular transitions. When a molecule contains substantial outlier temperatures, the sample-average temperature for the cases in which either only a single transition or no transitions were observed was replaced with the sample-median temperature.

Chapter 3

Results

3.1 Detection Fractions

Figure 3.1 shows the spectra of all 16 sources listed in order of increasing density of molecular lines. A wide dispersion in line richness is evident in the sample. B1-a and SVS 4-5 are very line-dense, followed by a collection of moderately rich sources: B1-c, IRAS 23238, L1455 IRS3, B5 IRS1, L1455 SMM1, IRAS 03235, L1014 IRS, IRAS 04108, and IRAS 03235. Finally, L1489, HH 300, IRAS 03271, IRAS 03253, and L1448 IRS1 are quite line-poor. Carbon chain molecules have a similar richness distribution across sources as was found for complex organic molecules by Bergner et al. (submitted). We find both line-rich (e.g. B1-a and B1-c) and line-poor (e.g. L1448 IRS1) sources in the Perseus star-forming region.

We detect linear chains, sulfur-bearing chains (i.e. C_nS), and cyanopolyynes. Specifically, we find that CS, CCS, CCCS, HC_3N , HC_5N , C_3H , and C_4H are detected in 16, 15, 7, 13, 6, 14, and 14 sources, respectively; this corresponds to detection percentages of 100%, 94%, 44%, 81%, 38%, 88%, and 88%. The spectrum for B1-a, a particularly line-rich source, with carbon chain identifications is shown in Figure 3.2. The remaining lines have been previously identified as arising from methanol, COMs, CO isotopologues, CN, and other small molecules, and are the subject of previous studies (cf. Öberg et al., 2014; Graninger et al., 2016).

Figure 3.1: IRAM 30 m spectra of the low-mass YSO sample shown in order of line richness. Reproduced from Bergner et al. (submitted).

Figure 3.3 shows the spectral windows containing CCS lines, which are highlighted by a dotted red line. The varying line strengths across individual sources is evident. Spectral windows containing lines of the remaining molecules are shown in the Appendix (Figures A.1-A.6). A summary of the individual molecular transitions observed per source and the total detection fraction per molecule are shown in Tables 3.1 and 3.2. We note that CS and CCS are detected in nearly all of the sources, while larger molecules such as CCCS and HC₅N are detected in < 50% of the sample. L1448 IRS1 is found to be a particularly line-poor source with no carbon chain detections.

Integrated intensities and upper limits for each observed line were determined by fitting single Gaussians to each feature (as described in Section 2.4) and are listed in Tables A.1-A.6 in the Appendix.

Table 3.1: Molecule Line Detections per Source

Source	CS [# / 3]	CCS [# / 3]	CCCS [# / 2]	HC ₃ N [# / 2]	HC ₅ N [# / 4]	C ₃ H [# / 4]	C ₄ H* [# / 4]
B1-a	3	3	2	2	1	4	4
SVS 4-5	3	3	2	2	4	4	4
B1-c	3	3	2	1	2	4	2
IRAS 23238+7401	3	2	1	1	2	4	4
L1455 IRS3	3	2	0	1	0	4	2
B5 IRS 1	3	3	0	2	2	4	4
L1455 SMM1	3	3	2	1	0	4	4
IRAS 03245+3002	3	3	2	1	3	4	4
L1014 IRS	3	2	0	1	0	4	3
IRAS 04108+2803	3	1	0	0	0	2	2
IRAS 03235+3004	3	3	1	2	0	4	4
L1489 IRS	3	2	0	2	0	0	0
HH 300	3	2	0	0	0	2	2
IRAS 03271+3013	2	1	0	1	0	1	4
IRAS 03254+3050	2	1	0	0	2	1	4
L1448 IRS1	3	0	0	0	0	0	0

* C₄H data taken from Graninger et al. (2016) with an additional new detection in source IRAS 03254+3050.

Figure 3.3: Zoomed-in spectra of CCS toward the low-mass YSO sample. Rest frequencies derived assuming the characteristic velocity of each source.

Table 3.2: Summary of Molecular Detections in the 16 Sources

Molecule	Sources [# / 16]
CS	16 [100%]
CCS	15 [94%]
CCCS	7 [44%]
HC ₃ N	13 [81%]
HC ₅ N	6 [38%]
C ₃ H	14 [88%]
C ₄ H	14 [88%]

3.2 Carbon Chain Rotational Temperatures

For sources with at least two line detections for a given molecule, rotational excitation temperatures were derived using the rotational diagram method. Rotational diagrams for CCS are shown in Figure 3.4 and diagrams for all detected molecules are presented in the Appendix (Figures A.7-A.9). Derived temperatures spanned from 7 K to 42 K, with CCS having the lowest temperature and HC₅N the highest. The complete data, along with source and species mean temperatures, are listed in Table 3.3. CCS and HC₃N have relatively stable temperature distributions across sources as indicated by their low standard deviations of 1.8 and 1.3 K, respectively. The mean rotational temperatures of these molecules thus serve as excellent substitutes for sources lacking sufficient detections for independent temperature derivation using rotational diagrams. In a few cases, we identified sources with abnormal rotational temperatures for one or more molecules. If these were based on low signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) lines and therefore very uncertain, the sample-median was used for that source and associated molecules, which was the case for CCCS in L1455 SMM1. No rotational diagrams could be constructed for CS and C₃H due to the small upper-level energy range of the observed transitions. For C₃H, the column densities were calculated using the mean C₄H rotational temperature reported by Graninger et al. (2016) and for CS, the mean CCS rotational temperature was used. These choices were motivated by the fact

Figure 3.4: Rotational diagrams for CCS. Black circles indicate detections and gray triangles indicate upper limits. Black dashed lines represent the fits to the data. When a line could not be fit, a rotational temperature was assumed as described in the text and is shown as a gray dashed line. L1448 IRS 1, which had no CCS line detections, is not shown.

that C_3H/C_4H and CS/CCS belong to the same families of unsaturated carbon chains and should exhibit similar chemistries. For HC_5N , only two sources had a sufficient number of detections to calculate rotational temperatures. However, these temperatures are uncertain and seem, especially in the case of IRAS 03245+3002, to be anomalously high, considering that Watanabe et al. (2015) found a rotational temperature of only ≈ 26 K for HC_5N in the young massive protostar NGC 2264 CMM3. As it has an uncertainty of ± 62 K, the 90 K temperature derived for IRAS 03245+3002 is considered an upper limit and the rotational temperature derived for SVS 4-5 is used for all of our sources with HC_5N line detections. Since SVS 4-5 shows elevated rotational temperatures for several molecules relative to the sample, the HC_5N column densities are likely underestimated, so column density calculations are also performed using the mean species temperature for HC_3N . In summary, the rotational temperatures adopted for sources that were undeterminable via rotation diagrams were: 9 K for CS and CCS , 16 K for $CCCS$, 13 K for HC_3N , 13 and 42 K for HC_5N , 10 K for C_3H and C_4H .

Based on the results summarized in Table 3.3, there is a spread in species mean temperatures across molecules of 8.9–18.6 K and a slightly narrower range in source mean temperatures of 10.0–18.6 K. However, as noted previously, L1455 SMM1 has an outlier temperature for $CCCS$ and SVS 4-5 exhibits elevated temperatures for most molecules. If these protostars are excluded, all remaining sources have typical mean temperatures of ≈ 10 –14 K. There does not appear to be any significant trend between the mean rotational temperature of the sources and their line-richness. Specifically, the line-rich sources B1-a and IRAS 23238+7401, moderately line-dense source B5 IRS1, and line-poor source HH 300 all have approximately the same rotational temperature. For the sulfur-bearing chains, temperature increases with molecular size with $CCCS$ having a rotational temperature more than double that of CCS . This trend of increased temperature with molecular size exhibited by the C_nS species is also true for each individual source.

Table 3.3: Carbon Chain Rotational Temperatures in K for the 16 Sources

Source	CCS	CCCS	HC ₃ N	HC ₅ N	C ₄ H*	Source Mean
B1-a	10 [1]	16 [6]	12 [2]	<i>13 [1] / 42 [9]</i>	9.6 [1.7]	11.9 [2.9]
SVS 4-5	10 [1]	12 [5]	14 [3]	42 [9] ?	15 [3]	18.6 [13.2]
B1-c	7 [1]	10 [6]	<i>13 [1]</i>	<i>13 [1] / 42 [9]</i>	10 [2]	10.0 [2.4]
IRAS 23238+7401	8 [1]	<i>16 [6]</i>	<i>13 [1]</i>	<i>13 [1] / 42 [9]</i>	10 [1]	11.8 [3.5]
L1455 IRS3	9 [1]	<i>16 [6]</i>	<i>13 [1]</i>	<i>13 [1] / 42 [9]</i>	10 [2]	12.0 [3.2]
B5 IRS 1	11 [1]	<i>16 [6]</i>	11 [2]	<i>13 [1] / 42 [9]</i>	9.5 [1.0]	11.9 [2.8]
L1455 SMM1	9 [1]	37 [11] ?	<i>13 [1]</i>	<i>13 [1] / 42 [9]</i>	11 [7]	17.5 [13.1]
IRAS 03245+3002	12 [2]	18 [4]	<i>13 [1]</i>	<i>13 [1] / 42 [9]</i>	10 [4]	13.3 [3.4]
L1014 IRS	6 [1]	<i>16 [6]</i>	<i>13 [1]</i>	<i>13 [1] / 42 [9]</i>	6.9 [1.0]	10.5 [4.8]
IRAS 04108+2803	<i>9 [2]</i>	<i>16 [6]</i>	<i>13 [1]</i>	<i>13 [1] / 42 [9]</i>	10 [2]	<i>12.0 [3.2]</i>
IRAS 03235+3004	9 [1]	<i>16 [6]</i>	14 [3]	<i>13 [1] / 42 [9]</i>	10 [3]	12.3 [3.3]
L1489 IRS	<i>9 [2]</i>	<i>16 [6]</i>	<i>13 [1]</i>	<i>13 [1] / 42 [9]</i>	10 [2]	<i>12.0 [3.2]</i>
HH 300	7 [1]	<i>16 [6]</i>	<i>13 [1]</i>	<i>13 [1] / 42 [9]</i>	10 [2]	11.5 [3.9]
IRAS 03271+3013	<i>9 [2]</i>	<i>16 [6]</i>	<i>13 [1]</i>	<i>13 [1] / 42 [9]</i>	10 [3]	<i>12.0 [3.2]</i>
IRAS 03254+3050	<i>9 [2]</i>	<i>16 [6]</i>	<i>13 [1]</i>	<i>13 [1] / 42 [9]</i>	<i>10 [1.6][†]</i>	<i>12.0 [3.2]</i>
L1448 IRS1	<i>9 [2]</i>	<i>16 [6]</i>	<i>13 [1]</i>	<i>13 [1] / 42 [9]</i>	10 [2]	<i>12.0 [3.2]</i>
Species Mean	8.9 [1.8]	18.6 [9.6]	12.3 [1.3]	–	10.1 [1.5]	

Note: *C₄H data are taken from Graninger et al. (2016) with an additional new detection from source IRAS 03254+3050 (denoted with a †). Uncertainties are reported in brackets. T_{rot} values in italics are assumed rotational temperatures and are based either on the sample-averaged temperature with standard deviation errors or, in the presence of outlier temperature(s), the median sample temperature. C₃H and CS are omitted due to difficulties (e.g. too narrow spacings of E_u) in determining rotational temperatures. Species and source means are reported using measured rotational temperatures and those reported in italics represent means using adopted temperatures. Question marks indicate either outlier temperatures as in the case for CCCS or suspiciously high temperatures as for HC₅N.

3.3 Column Densities and Abundances

3.3.1 Column Densities

Figure 3.5a shows the column densities derived for each molecule in all sources for both detections and upper limits, in which column densities are ordered by decreasing CS column density. All molecules except HC₅N have multiple detections that are substantially larger than the non-detection upper limits and the resulting ranges of derived column densities span at least an order of magnitude. The detections of HC₅N are close to the non-detection upper limits. Thus, the upper limits for this molecule are not very constraining, and the

variability in column density of this molecule cannot be well understood from this sample.

The HC_5N column densities are reported using the SVS 4-5 derived rotational temperature of 42 K in Table 3.4 and Figure 3.5a but HC_5N column densities are up to $10\times$ higher when calculated using the HC_3N temperature of 13 K (see Appendix A.9).

The sources B1-c, SVS 4-5, and B1-a, which are shown as the first three bars in Figure 3.5a indicate enhanced carbon chain column densities relative to the other sources. All seven molecules are detected toward these sources and the derived column densities are high and often an order of magnitude in excess of the sample medians. In contrast, L1448 IRS1 and L1489 IRS have only one and three carbon chain detections, respectively. While HH 300 shows enhancement in sulfur-bearing molecules CS and CCS as well as carbon chain radicals C_3H and C_4H , no cyanopolyynes are observed toward this source. L1489 IRS also displays an enhancement in CS and CCS along with HC_3N , but lacks detections of the carbon chains C_3H and C_4H . Detectability varies significantly across molecules with less complex species like CS (100%) and HC_3N (81%) having higher detection fractions than more complex molecules of the same family such as CCCS (44%) and HC_5N (38%). CS, CCS, HC_3N , and C_4H have relatively high column densities and all have detection fractions above 80%, indicating that they are both common and abundant in low-mass protostellar environments.

Table 3.4: Carbon Chain Column Densities in cm^{-2} for the 16 Sources

Source	CS	CCS	CCCS	HC ₃ N	HC ₅ N	C ₃ H	C ₄ H*
B1-a	2.5 [1.2]×10 ¹³	5.8 [1.7]×10 ¹²	6.1 [4.9]×10 ¹¹	4.1 [1.2]×10 ¹²	1.3 [1.0]×10 ¹¹	3.9 [2.1]×10 ¹¹	2.5 [0.6]×10 ¹³
SVS 4-5	5.3 [2.6]×10 ¹³	3.5 [1.3]×10 ¹²	1.4 [1.7]×10 ¹²	1.0 [0.3]×10 ¹³	2.6 [1.2]×10 ¹¹	4.1 [2.2]×10 ¹¹	2.2 [0.4]×10 ¹³
B1-c	9.9 [5.0]×10 ¹³	6.2 [2.9]×10 ¹²	1.3 [4.9]×10 ¹¹	4.7 [2.4]×10 ¹²	3.7 [3.2]×10 ¹¹	4.3 [2.3]×10 ¹¹	2.7 [0.2]×10 ¹³
IRAS 23238+7401	9.3 [4.6]×10 ¹²	1.7 [0.2]×10 ¹²	1.5 [3.3]×10 ¹¹	3.6 [1.8]×10 ¹²	2.0 [1.5]×10 ¹¹	2.1 [1.2]×10 ¹¹	1.4 [2.2]×10 ¹³
L1455 IRS3	4.3 [2.1]×10 ¹²	1.4 [0.2]×10 ¹²	< 1.1×10 ¹¹	7.3 [3.8]×10 ¹¹	< 1.3×10 ¹¹	2.5 [1.4]×10 ¹¹	1.1 [0.3]×10 ¹³
B5 IRS 1	8.5 [4.2]×10 ¹²	1.7 [0.5]×10 ¹²	< 1.8×10 ¹¹	3.2 [1.0]×10 ¹²	3.0 [2.6]×10 ¹¹	4.0 [2.3]×10 ¹¹	3.6 [0.5]×10 ¹³
L1455 SMM1	1.1 [0.6]×10 ¹²	4.3 [1.4]×10 ¹²	1.8 [0.1]×10 ¹¹	2.7 [1.4]×10 ¹²	< 1.3×10 ¹¹	3.5 [1.9]×10 ¹¹	1.8 [0.5]×10 ¹³
IRAS 03245+3002	1.7 [0.8]×10 ¹³	3.3 [1.0]×10 ¹²	7.0 [2.5]×10 ¹¹	4.0 [2.1]×10 ¹²	2.3 [2.2]×10 ¹¹	1.7 [0.9]×10 ¹¹	1.6 [0.7]×10 ¹³
L1014 IRS	2.8 [1.4]×10 ¹²	2.1 [0.8]×10 ¹²	< 1.1×10 ¹¹	4.9 [2.5]×10 ¹¹	< 8.5×10 ¹⁰	2.0 [1.1]×10 ¹¹	3.2 [0.8]×10 ¹³
IRAS 04108+2803	2.5 [1.3]×10 ¹²	6.0 [4.7]×10 ¹¹	< 1.5×10 ¹¹	< 6.0×10 ¹⁰	< 1.2×10 ¹¹	1.9 [1.1]×10 ¹¹	0.64 [0.24]×10 ¹³
IRAS 03235+3004	4.4 [2.2]×10 ¹²	2.2 [0.7]×10 ¹²	2.0 [4.3]×10 ¹¹	3.7 [1.1]×10 ¹²	< 1.4×10 ¹¹	5.5 [2.9]×10 ¹¹	3.8 [1.5]×10 ¹³
L1489 IRS	5.9 [2.9]×10 ¹²	5.4 [5.2]×10 ¹¹	< 1.1×10 ¹¹	3.8 [3.9]×10 ¹¹	< 2.2×10 ¹¹	< 1.3×10 ¹¹	< 0.32×10 ¹³
HH 300	2.9 [1.4]×10 ¹²	1.2 [0.8]×10 ¹²	< 1.7×10 ¹¹	< 1.4×10 ¹¹	< 1.8×10 ¹¹	1.4 [0.7]×10 ¹¹	1.0 [3.2]×10 ¹³
IRAS 03271+3013	2.9 [1.5]×10 ¹²	3.0 [2.4]×10 ¹¹	< 1.1×10 ¹¹	1.9 [1.0]×10 ¹²	< 1.4×10 ¹¹	4.3 [2.3]×10 ¹¹	1.4 [0.5]×10 ¹³
IRAS 03254+3050	1.8 [0.9]×10 ¹²	2.3 [1.8]×10 ¹¹	< 1.5×10 ¹¹	< 9.3×10 ¹⁰	1.8 [1.5]×10 ¹¹	1.9 [1.1]×10 ¹¹	1.4 [0.9]×10 ¹³
L1448 IRS1	2.1 [1.1]×10 ¹²	< 8.5×10 ¹⁰	< 1.0×10 ¹¹	< 6.8×10 ¹⁰	< 1.1×10 ¹¹	< 0.8×10 ¹¹	<0.73×10 ¹³
Species Mean	1.42 [2.54]×10 ¹³	2.34 [1.84]×10 ¹²	4.81 [4.33]×10 ¹¹	3.29 [2.48]×10 ¹²	2.39 [0.74]×10 ¹¹	3.08 [1.29]×10 ¹¹	2.02 [1.00]×10 ¹³

*From Graninger et al. (2016) with an additional new detection from source IRAS 03254+3050. Column densities reported for HC₅N are calculated using $T_{\text{rot}} = 42$ [9] K derived from SVS 4-5. Uncertainties are reported in brackets. Species mean column densities are reported using only calculated column densities (i.e. no upper limits) with uncertainties given by their standard deviations.

Figure 3.5: a) Observed column densities for each molecule. b) Fractional abundances with respect to hydrogen. For both panels, detections are shown in blue and upper limits in gray. Since they lack measured envelope masses, SVS 4-5, IRAS 23238, L1014 IRS, HH 300, and IRAS 04108 are omitted from the bottom panel. In each case, the molecules are ordered according to descending CS column density. This corresponds to an ordering for a: B1-c, SVS 4-5, B1-a, IRAS 03245, IRAS 23238, B5 IRS1, L1489 IRS, IRAS 03235, L1455 IRS3, IRAS 03271, HH 300, L1014 IRS, IRAS 04108, L1448 IRS1, IRAS 03254, and L1455 SMM1; and an ordering for b: L1455 IRS3, L1489 IRS, B1-a, IRAS 03254, B1-c, IRAS 03245, IRAS 03271, B5 IRS1, IRAS 03235, L1455 SMM1, and L1448 IRS1.

3.3.2 Fractional Abundance Calculation

To compare our observational results for low-mass YSO chemical abundances with current theoretical predictions, we need to calculate fractional abundances with respect to atomic hydrogen. Thus, we first need to determine the hydrogen column density that is contained within the beam. We assume a spherically symmetric physical model of a low-mass YSO with power-law density profile:

$$n_{\text{H}}(r) = n_{\text{M}_{\text{env}}} \left(\frac{r}{1000\text{AU}} \right)^{-\alpha} \quad (3.1)$$

where $n_{\text{M}_{\text{env}}}$ is a normalizing constant based on the envelope mass of each source. To account for the individual envelope masses of our sources, we assume that all of the envelope material is molecular hydrogen. Based on the median values determined from radiative transfer

modeling of low-mass protostars in Jørgensen et al. (2002), we assume $\alpha = 1.5$, typical of a free-falling core. To determine the total number of H atoms within the beam for a typical protostar with radial density profile $n_H(r)$ and emitting area $A(r)$ at each radius, we integrate from minimum to maximum radii:

$$\eta_H = \int_{r_{\min}}^{r_{\max}} A(r)n_H(r)dr. \quad (3.2)$$

For our sources, we assume $r_{\min} = 1$ AU and a maximum extent of $r_{\max} = 20000$ AU, which is consistent with the values adopted in Jørgensen et al. (2002).

Then, the beam-averaged hydrogen column density is given by:

$$N_H = \frac{\eta_H}{\pi r_b^2} \quad (3.3)$$

where r_b is the beam radius. We assume a $12''$ beam radius based on the size of the observing beam (see Section 2.2) and a distance of 250 pc to Perseus (Schlafly et al., 2014) and 140 pc to Taurus (Torres et al., 2007). To account for the cylindrical line of sight, we express $A(r)$ as:

$$A(r) = \begin{cases} 4\pi r^2, & r \leq r_b \\ 2\pi \left[r_b^2 + \left(r - \sqrt{r^2 - r_b^2} \right)^2 \right], & r > r_b \end{cases}$$

While the radius is smaller than the beam radius, the emitting surface corresponds to the surface area of a sphere at that radius. Beyond the beam radius, the emitting surface consists of spherical caps in front of and behind a sphere of radius r_b . These caps have a fixed base radius r_b and a height that varies depending on radius. This methodology is adapted from Bergner et al. (submitted).

Then, the species specific column densities are simply given by the ratio:

$$f_X = \frac{N_X}{N_H}. \quad (3.4)$$

Using this method, the beam is determined to contain $\approx 50\%$ and $\approx 46\%$ of the protostellar envelope mass for Perseus and Taurus sources, respectively. To test the effect of selecting different r_{\max} values, beam fractions were calculated for $r_{\max} = 10000$ AU. For Perseus sources, there was a difference of about 8% in beam fraction and about 5% for Taurus sources.

Fractional abundances with respect to hydrogen column density are shown in Figure 3.5b. Since envelope masses are not available for SVS 4-5, IRAS 23238, L1014 IRS, HH 300, and IRAS 04108, these sources are omitted from the comparison. In terms of abundances, B1-c becomes more consistent with the other sources, while B1-a still shows enhanced carbon chains. Unfortunately, SVS 4-5 does not have data for its envelope mass so we are unable to determine if this carbon chain enhancement persists relative to the amount of material in its envelope. L1455 IRS3 and L1489 IRS also display significant overabundances of carbon chains.

3.4 Sample Statistics

3.4.1 Median Column Densities and Abundances

We calculate median column densities and abundances using both detections only and detections with upper limits. Median abundances calculated using detections only neglect the information provided by upper limits and thus risk over-estimating the median occurrences. Hence, survival analysis using the Kaplan-Meier (KM) estimator of the survival function with left censorship was performed. In this method, all detections and non-detections are ordered and then the values of positive detections are used to divide the total range of values into intervals. Upper limits within an interval are counted as having the lower delimiting

value of the interval. Equivalently, each positive detection is weighted by the number of upper limits that occur between it and the next largest positive detection. Further details can be found in Feigelson and Nelson (1985).

Since the survival function is discrete, median abundances are calculated by linear interpolation between the values above and below where the cumulative density function (CDF) is equal to 0.5. However, medians cannot be computed via the KM estimator for samples with only upper limits in the lowest 50% of values since the first positive detection occurs after the cumulative density has already exceeded 0.5. In this sample, this applies to CCCS and HC₅N. To circumvent this limitation, we calculate medians using the KM estimator with the lowest value assigned a “detection” status, regardless of its true identity as a detection or a non-detection. Doing so may result in elevated estimates for median values, but as seen in Figure 3.6, this method still provides a more realistic estimate of the median than using detections only.

Table 3.5: Median Column Densities and Fractional Abundances

	Median Column Densities (10 ¹² cm ⁻²)		Median abundances (10 ⁻¹²)
	Detections Only	Survival Analysis	Survival Analysis
CS	4.4 ^{11.2} _{2.7}	4.4 ^{11.2} _{2.7}	33.7 ^{76.0} _{15.2}
CCS	1.7 ^{3.4} _{0.90}	1.6 ^{3.3} _{0.54}	5.9 ^{9.0} _{2.7}
CCCS	0.20 ^{0.66} _{0.17}	0.096 ^{0.18} _{0.048}	0.16 ^{0.67} _{0.05}
HC ₃ N	3.4 ^{4.0} _{1.6}	1.9 ^{3.7} _{0.060}	5.8 ^{11.2} _{1.5}
HC ₅ N	0.23 ^{0.28} _{0.19}	0.083 ^{0.22} _{0.042}	0.22 ^{0.35} _{0.06}
C ₃ H	0.30 ^{0.41} _{0.19}	0.21 ^{0.40} _{0.17}	0.59 ^{2.0} _{0.16}
C ₄ H	17.0 ^{26.5} _{14.0}	14.0 ^{25.0} _{8.7}	44.6 ^{89.5} _{17.4}

Note: Lower and upper quartiles are shown to the right of the medians.

Median column densities for each molecule are shown in Figure 3.6a and Table 3.5 for both methods. There is a clear difference between the medians calculated from detections only and those determined using survival analysis, demonstrating the importance of using the constraints provided by non-detections.

Figure 3.6: a) Median column densities of each molecule, calculated using detections only (light gray) and using survival analysis (dark blue). b) Median fractional abundances for each molecule calculated with survival analysis. Error bars span the first and third quartile determined using survival analysis.

Median column densities span three orders of magnitude. For the sulfur-bearing chains, each additional carbon atom leads to approximately an order of magnitude reduction in the median column density. Similarly, the addition of two C atoms from HC₃N to HC₅N leads to a reduction of one order of magnitude. For the carbon chain radicals, however, the addition of one C atom from C₃H to C₄H leads to a two order of magnitude increase in column density.

Median abundances calculated using survival analysis are shown in Figure 3.6b. The median fractional abundances also span three orders of magnitude and exhibit the same trends as found for the median column densities. The distribution of abundances, reflected in the error bars spanning the lower and upper quartiles, is tighter for the small sulfur-bearing molecules CS and CCS than for both the nitrogen-bearing chains and the carbon

chain radicals.

3.4.2 Abundance Distributions

The distributions of column densities and fractional abundances reveal variations in chemistry among sources and between different molecules. Figure 3.7a shows a histogram of each molecule’s column density. Most molecules exhibit column densities which span an order of magnitude or more. However, C_3H , C_4H , and HC_5N are exceptions — the distributions are narrow. The lower and upper quartiles for column densities are listed in Table 3.5. CCS, CCCS, and HC_3N have reasonably large spreads with a factor of ~ 3 – 4 difference in lower and upper quartile values, while HC_5N , C_3H , and C_4H are more tightly concentrated with only a factor of ~ 2 in quartile spread.

When plotted in terms of fractional abundances, the distribution of column densities broadens for all species, except HC_3N . The lower and upper quartiles in Table 3.5 reflect this trend as well. This broadening is particularly prominent for CCCS, which in terms of abundance, spans an order of magnitude between upper and lower quartiles.

Figure 3.7: a) Histograms of observed column densities for each molecule. b) Abundances with respect to hydrogen column density. For both panels, detections are shown in blue and upper limits in light gray.

3.4.3 Correlation Studies

To explore chemical relationships between carbon chains, we searched for correlations between different chains. Strong positive correlations are expected for chemically related molecules (e.g. if one forms from another) or for molecules that depend similarly on an underlying parameter such as envelope mass or temperature. When comparing column densities, some correlation is typically expected since all molecules usually increase with an increasing total column density along a line of sight. We use the column density correlation strengths to infer which molecules are more closely related with the understanding that some of the observed correlation may be due to source mass rather than chemical similarity.

Additionally, correlations of column densities with physical properties may also provide insight into the underlying chemistry. Thus, we checked for correlations between envelope mass and bolometric luminosity with carbon chain column densities. Since the majority of sources reside in Perseus, we also investigated the influence of star-forming region on our correlations (i.e. if we find tighter or looser correlations considering only sources which are members of Perseus). The impact of star-forming region on these correlations can provide information regarding the influence of the physical conditions from which protostars form and in which they reside on the observed carbon chain chemistry. Hence, Perseus sources are shown as circles and sources from other star-forming regions are indicated with stars in the correlation plots.

We calculate the Spearman’s rank correlation coefficient for each carbon chain with one another and list the results in Table 3.6. Unlike Pearson’s correlation, which characterizes linear relationships, Spearman’s correlation assesses monotonic relationships or alternatively, the rank order between two variables. Spearman’s correlation was chosen since we do not have any prior expectation of linear correlation and the fact that Spearman’s correlation is less sensitive to outlier values than Pearson’s. Only detections were used for calculating the correlations. Figure 3.8 shows scatter plots of each molecule’s column density plotted

against one another. For completeness, the Pearson coefficients for the molecule-to-molecule comparisons were also calculated and are shown in Table A.7 in the Appendix.

The cyanopolyynes are generally well-correlated with the sulfur-bearing chains. Specifically, the correlations between CS/HC₃N and CCS/HC₃N have $r = 0.80$ and $r = 0.75$, respectively. This finding suggests that the production chemistry of CS and CCS is closely related to that of HC₃N in low-mass protostars. If so, these chemistries, as they are in cold clouds (Fuente et al., 1990; Suzuki et al., 1992), may also be closely related during low-mass star formation. More moderate correlations exist between similar families of carbon chains. We find moderate positive correlations of $r = 0.55$ between CS/CCS, which are closely related (e.g. Bergin and Langer, 1997; Aikawa et al., 2001), as well as between C₃H/C₄H with $r = 0.63$. We also find a correlation of $r = 0.63$ between CCS/C₄H.

There are several notable instances in which correlations are absent. For example, we do not find significant correlations between larger molecules of the same family, such as CCS/CCCS and HC₃N/HC₅N. If the formation chemistry of these species is related (see Discussion 4.1), it is surprising that we do not observe correlations. Although, larger molecules such as CCCS and HC₅N have more upper limits and lower SNR detections, potentially influencing the observed lack of correlation.

There are a few outliers which impact the strength of observed correlations. The source L1455 SMM1 has a much higher CCS/CS column density ratio compared to the typical CCS/CS ratio, which reduces this correlation. The source IRAS 03254+3050 has both much lower C₄H/HC₅N and C₄H/C₃H ratios than the typical source, reducing these overall correlations.

Figure 3.8: Column densities (cm^{-2}) of each molecule plotted against one another. Detections are shown in black and upper limits as gray arrows. Sources which are members of Perseus are shown as circles and all other sources are represented by stars. Spearman correlation coefficients using all detected sources are displayed in the bottom right corners of each scatter plot.

Table 3.6: Spearman Coefficients for Molecule-Molecule Column Density Correlations

	CS	CCS	CCCS	HC ₃ N	HC ₅ N	C ₃ H
C ₄ H	0.39 [14]	0.63 [14]	-0.07 [7]	0.23 [11]	0.59 [7]	0.63 [14]
C ₃ H	0.40 [14]	0.39 [14]	-0.14 [7]	0.34 [11]	0.64 [7]	
HC ₅ N	0.39 [7]	0.31 [7]	-0.10 [5]	0.14 [6]		
HC ₃ N	0.80 [12]	0.75 [13]	0.39 [7]			
CCCS	0.11 [7]	-0.14 [7]				
CCS	0.55 [15]					

Note: Brackets indicate the number of sources with detections for both molecules.

All molecules except CCCS correlate positively with envelope mass as shown in Figure 3.9. This correlation is, in part, because more molecules are present in lines of sight containing additional material. The negative correlation reported for CCCS is likely the result of scatter due to a fewer number of lower SNR detections. The largest correlation coefficient is for HC₅N, but due to the low sample size, this correlation is not significant. There are strong correlations for CCS ($r = 0.80$) and HC₃N ($r = 0.78$), with the remaining molecules showing smaller positive correlations. These positive correlations with envelope mass are expected, since carbon chains are thought to form through gas-phase chemistry and emit from the cold, protostellar envelope (Herbst and van Dishoeck, 2009) and therefore, should trace the envelope mass very well.

Most of the upper limits are consistent with the observed correlations. L1448 IRS1 is a consistent upper limit outlier for all molecules besides CS. The other noteworthy outlier is the source IRAS 03254+3050 with an HC₃N upper limit that is an order of magnitude lower than the observed column densities.

Correlations with bolometric luminosity are slightly positive for all species as shown in Figure 3.10. In contrast to the envelope mass correlations, no single molecule stands out as particularly well-correlated with bolometric luminosity. This finding suggests that these weak correlations are not driven by chemistry, but rather by excess excitation and ice desorption, which affects all molecules around hotter protostars.

Figure 3.9: Column densities plotted against envelope mass. Upper limits due to non-detections are indicated by blue arrows. Sources which are members of Perseus are shown as circles and all other sources are represented by stars. Spearman correlation coefficients are shown in brackets in the lower right corner for all detections and detections in Perseus sources only. Double dashes indicate that the correlation remained the same when just considering Perseus sources. For the sake of visual clarity, the column densities for CS and C_4H are both scaled by 0.1.

The most obvious outlier in Figures 3.9 and 3.10 is L1448 IRS1, towards which only CS was detected despite being one of the most massive and luminous of our sample. Massive sources are more likely to be young stars (Hatchell et al., 2007), so its unusual characteristics could be related to an early evolutionary stage. This source was also found to be lacking in COMs by Bergner et al. (submitted), further indicating this source as particularly unusual. For HC_3N , two of the three Taurus sources have outlier upper limits, which are substantially lower than the observed column densities. One Taurus detection was also about an order of magnitude lower than the Perseus detections; it is possible that there is a separate luminosity correlation for Taurus sources.

We also investigated the potential effect of star-forming region (SFR). However, since most of our sources were in Perseus, this comparison was somewhat limited. For the molecule-

Figure 3.10: Column densities plotted against bolometric luminosity. Upper limits due to non-detections are indicated by blue arrows. Sources which are members of Perseus are shown as circles and all other sources are represented by a star. Spearman correlation coefficients are shown in brackets in the lower right corner for all detections and detections in Perseus sources only. For the sake of visual clarity, the column densities for CS and C₄H are both scaled by 0.1.

to-molecule correlations as well as for correlations between envelope mass and bolometric luminosity, no substantial differences were found when only considering the Perseus sample. For most molecules, the Spearman correlation coefficients remained approximately the same or decreased, potentially due to the fact that there were only a few sources in other SFRs. Thus, removing or adding a few sources did little to change observed correlations. Importantly, however, no systematic tightening or loosening of correlations was observed, which implies that there does not seem to be any special conditions influencing the protostellar chemistry in Perseus relative to other SFRs in our sample. The Perseus-only correlations are shown in full in Appendix Table A.8.

Chapter 4

Discussion

Here we review the key findings from our observations and discuss the implications for low-mass protostellar carbon chain chemistry. We first discuss the formation chemistry of each carbon chain family in light of our observational results and known formation pathways. Considering our correlation results, we identify species necessary for production of certain molecules and check if they exhibit the expected correlations. In this way, we can comment on the efficiency of proposed production pathways. We then compare our observations against carbon chain abundances in cold clouds, carbon chain-rich protostars, and warm-up models.

4.1 Carbon Chain Chemistry

The observed carbon chain abundances provide constraints on the chemistry that could produce them. We note that such a chemistry must have some general characteristics. It must be general enough to always produce some carbon chains, as we detect them in almost all sources. The formation and/or destruction chemistry must also be sensitive to some aspects of the protostellar environment and/or evolutionary stage since we see order-of-magnitude variations across the sample. It is likely bottom-up chemistry, since we observe a decreasing abundance with size within families (the C_3H/C_4H anomaly is fairly well understood), as shown in Figure 4.1. Since all of our chosen sources are approximately at the same evo-

lutionary stage, the chemical influence of protostellar evolution may be diminished in this sample. Finally, the lack of correlations between the pure hydrocarbon chains and the C_nS and $HC_{2n+1}N$ molecules suggest that there are multiple, fairly independent carbon chain chemistries that affect the final carbon chain composition in a protostellar envelope.

Figure 4.1: Number of carbon atoms versus median column densities. Error bars span the first and third quartile determined by survival analysis. As they each contain three carbon atoms, $CCCS$, C_3H , and HC_3N have small horizontal offsets for the sake of visual clarity.

4.1.1 Carbon Chains

The main pathway for forming polyynes of increasing chain length with an even number of carbon atoms involves successive reactions with the radical C_2H via $C_2H + C_{2n}H_2 \rightarrow C_{2n+2}H_2 + H$ (Agundez et al., 2017). Once the polyynes are formed, the corresponding radicals form directly from photodissociation (Silva et al., 2008). Hence, when $n = 1$, diacetylene (C_4H_2) is synthesized in the above reaction and then photodissociates to form C_4H . The polyynone formation reaction is efficient at low temperatures (Chastaing et al.,

1998) and C_4H_2 is easily photodissociated owing to its large absorption cross section in the ultraviolet (Ferradaz et al., 2009). Additional C_4H is produced by reactions with C_2 via $C_2 + C_{2n}H_2 \rightarrow C_{2n+2}H + H$, as the addition of C_2 to the C_2H_2 subunit occurs rapidly at low temperatures (Canosa et al., 2007). The production of unsaturated carbon chains with an odd number of carbon atoms occurs efficiently at low temperatures via reactions of neutral carbon atoms and CH radicals with C_2H_2 (Chastaing et al., 2001; Loison and Bergeat, 2009). In particular, C_3H can form by the neutral-neutral reaction $C + C_2H_2 \rightarrow C_3H + H$ (Kaiser et al., 1997, 1999).

The observed trend of the C_4H median column density being two orders of magnitude in excess of that of C_3H is consistent with previous observations (Gratier et al., 2016) and model predictions (Hassel et al., 2011). The weak correlation observed between C_4H and CCS is consistent with the fact that both molecules have at least one pathway which depends on the C_2H radical (see Section 4.1.3 for sulfur chemistry discussion). We do not observe a $CCCS/C_3H$ correlation, as might be expected from the proposed $C_3H + S^+$ formation pathway (Suzuki et al., 1992). However, since the sulfur chemistry may vary from protostar-to-protostar, it is difficult to speculate on the reasons for the absence of this correlation.

There is no observed correlation between C_3H and CS. As both of these molecules have at least one reaction that depends on the CH radical, it is tempting to suggest that C_3H is forming more efficiently via reactions involving neutral carbon atoms rather than CH radicals in our protostars. CS was detected in all protostars, indicating the presence of an active sulfur chemistry and the CH radical, which are necessary for its formation. However, since we did not search for C_2H_2 , an important reactant needed in addition to CH for C_3H production, such a claim of a more efficient neutral carbon formation pathway of C_3H is tenuous. If observations of C_2H_2 in these sources were to indicate that C_2H_2 was indeed prevalent, the above argument would be significantly strengthened.

4.1.2 Nitrogen-Bearing Chains

Cyanopolyynes observations in cold clouds can be well-reproduced by purely gas-phase models (Herbst and van Dishoeck, 2009). At low temperatures, the growth of cyanopolyynes occur via $\text{CN} + \text{C}_{2n}\text{H}_2 \rightarrow \text{HC}_{2n+1}\text{N} + \text{H}$, where C_2H_2 serves as the precursor of HC_3N , the polyynes C_4H_2 for HC_5N , and so on (Agundez et al., 2017). For $n = 1$, this reaction has been shown to be rapid at low temperatures (Seki et al., 1996), while other studies have confirmed that it proceeds without an activation barrier yielding HC_3N as its main product (Fukuzawa and Osamura, 1997; Choi et al., 2004). While no experimental results are available for $n \geq 2$, theoretical results indicate that this is an efficient low-temperature route for the production of large cyanopolyynes (Fukuzawa et al., 1998). For cyanopolyynes larger than HC_3N , there is another efficient low-temperature formation pathway with the radical C_3N via $\text{C}_3\text{N} + \text{C}_{2n}\text{H}_2 \rightarrow \text{HC}_{2n+3}\text{N} + \text{H}$ (Fournier, 2014).

The observed reduction in HC_5N median column density relative to HC_3N is consistent with previous protostellar observations and models, which have shown a similar trend (Hassel et al., 2011; Gratier et al., 2016). Since HC_3N , which has a formation pathway involving C_2H_2 , is common and abundant in the sample, we expect C_2H_2 to also be abundant. If C_2H_2 is abundant, our previous argument (in Section 4.1.1), suggesting that neutral C reactions are the dominant means of production for C_3H in our protostellar sample, is strengthened. However, we do not observe a correlation between $\text{HC}_3\text{N}/\text{C}_4\text{H}$, despite the fact that the formation pathways for both molecules involve the reactant C_2H_2 . Thus, the lack of this correlation suggests that there is protostellar variation in either the CN chemistry for HC_3N production or the C_2 molecule in the pathway for C_4H production (as the other formation mechanism for C_4H involves C_2H , the precursor of CCS , which is abundant in our sample, and is likely active in most of our protostars). The strong correlation observed between $\text{CCS}/\text{HC}_3\text{N}$ is not immediately explainable as the formation pathways for each do not share

the same reactants. This correlation may stem from the fact that the C_2H radical forms from ionization of C_2H_2 via $C_2H_2 + CR \rightarrow H + C_2H + CR^1$, a reaction expected to be efficient in the dense regions around protostars. However, a more careful survey of C_2H_2 and C_2H along with the cyanide and sulfur chemistry would be needed to confirm the origin of this CCS/ HC_3N correlation.

4.1.3 Sulfur-Bearing Chains

Originally discovered in TMC-1, CCS and CCCS established the existence of a new series of carbon chain molecules, C_nS (Saito et al., 1987; Yamamoto et al., 1987). Ohishi et al. (1991) found an abundance ratio for CCS/CCO in TMC-1 of 130, substantially in excess of the cosmic abundance ratio of sulfur to oxygen, which is only 1/20. This result implied a close relationship between sulfur chemistry and pure carbon chain chemistry and highlighted the importance of CCS for understanding the production of carbon chains in interstellar clouds. Despite the astrochemical significance of sulfur-bearing carbon chains, only a few observational studies have been undertaken to study the C_nS molecules.

Since the ionization potential of the sulfur atom is lower than that of the carbon atom, most of the sulfur atoms are ionized by the interstellar UV radiation in regions where there is only partial ionization of carbon atoms (Suzuki et al., 1992). Since S^+ does not interact with lower vibrational states ($v \leq 1$) of H_2 in cold clouds (Prasad and Huntress, 1982; Zanchet et al., 2013), the S^+ ion is expected to be abundant in the gas phase in regions that produce carbon chains (Suzuki et al., 1992). Reactions of hydrocarbons such as CH, C_2H , and C_3H with S^+ are major routes to produce CS, CCS, and CCCS, respectively (see Figure 11 in Suzuki et al., 1992).

The decreasing trend in median column density from $n = 1$ to $n = 3$ in the C_nS molecules is consistent with previous observations and model expectations (Hassel et al., 2011; Gratier

¹from <http://kida.obs.u-bordeaux1.fr/>

et al., 2016). The presence of a moderate correlation between CS/CCS is consistent with a formation pathway that depends on the S^+ ion. The presence of CCCS and its lack of correlation with CS and CCS implies that either *i)* a different formation chemistry is responsible for its production or *ii)* the C_3H, S^+ formation pathway is occurring inefficiently in these protostars. Considering that the reaction rates² for the C_3H, S^+ pathway are approximately the same as those for the CH and C_2H pathways, it is likely that any inefficiency in this reaction is due to insufficient amounts of the C_3H reactant. Additional observational studies of long ($n \geq 3$) sulfur-bearing chains and C_3H may be able to address this ambiguity and better characterize the C_3H abundances necessary for effective CCCS production in protostellar environments.

4.2 Comparison with Cold Clouds

We compare our carbon chain abundances against those found in dense cold clouds. Since these cold clouds represent the initial stages of low-mass star formation, comparing protostellar carbon chains abundances against these values may yield information on the carbon chain chemistry, helping to address questions of chemical inheritance.

Due to its relative closeness (≈ 140 pc) and rich molecular complexity, TMC-1 has been extensively observed to study the chemical processes taking place in dark clouds (e.g. Ohishi and Kaifu, 1998; Smith et al., 2004; McCarthy et al., 2006; Marcelino et al., 2007). TMC-1 carbon chain abundances are taken from Gratier et al. (2016), who use a Bayesian approach to compute updated abundances and uncertainties for all molecules detected in the Nobeyama spectral survey of TMC-1 from Kaifu et al. (2004). Figure 4.2 shows our carbon chain observations compared to the abundances found in TMC-1.

We find that all molecules and sources are underabundant, often by several orders of

²from <http://kida.obs.u-bordeaux1.fr/>

Figure 4.2: Observed fractional abundances compared with cold cloud TMC-1. Median fractional abundances are represented by red upward triangles and error bars span the first and third quartiles determined by survival analysis. Individual sources are represented by gray circles for detections and downward triangles for upper limits. Blue stars indicate TMC-1 observed fractional abundances from Gratier et al. (2016).

magnitude, relative to the TMC-1 abundances. This is an expected result, as we know that cold cores can efficiently form carbon chains via gas-phase chemistry. Our sample consists of protostars, which have evolved past the cold core phase and thus have lost many of their carbon chain molecules. It does not appear that we have lost all carbon chains by an equal amount. HC_5N experienced the largest decrease, followed by CCCS and HC_3N , while smaller decreases were seen for CCS , C_3H , and C_4H .

Next, we compare our abundance ratios against those found in cold clouds to assess if chemical relationships among different types of carbon chain molecules change during low-mass star formation. In a survey of 49 dark cloud cores, Suzuki et al. (1992) report positive column density correlations of $r = 0.77$ for $\text{CCS}/\text{HC}_3\text{N}$ and $r = 0.74$ for $\text{CCS}/\text{HC}_5\text{N}$. In our sample of low-mass YSOs, we find a comparable correlation between CCS and HC_3N of

$r = 0.75$ but a weak CCS/HC₅N correlation of $r = 0.31$. It is important to note that the correlation reported by Suzuki et al. (1992) is dominated by their quiescent sources. Thus our correlation suggests that there is a chemical similarity between cold core carbon chain chemistry and typical protostellar envelope carbon chain chemistry.

Figure 4.3 shows column density ratios between CCS and cyanopolyynes HC₃N and HC₅N for each protostar in our sample and the mean cold cloud ratios reported in Suzuki et al. (1992). Since Suzuki et al. (1992) do not report the spread seen in their ratios, we chose their sources with detections of CCS, HC₃N, and HC₅N and calculated the standard deviation in their reported column density ratios to estimate the observed variability. Relative to cold clouds, we find similar ratios for molecules CCS/HC₃N. When adopting a rotational temperature of 42 K for HC₅N, we find elevated ratios for most sources, often a factor of ~ 10 in excess of the average cold cloud ratio. However, when adopting the equally likely temperature of 13 K, the mean rotational temperature of HC₃N, these elevated ratios largely disappear. Therefore, until we can better constrain the HC₅N temperature, it is not possible to use these ratios to determine whether the sample, as a whole, is deviating from cold cloud core chemistry. However, in terms of typical CCS/HC₃N ratios, low-mass protostars still resemble cold clouds in the sense that sulfur- and nitrogen-bearing carbon chains still exhibit similar relationships.

4.3 Comparison with Carbon Chain-Rich Protostars

While the presence of unsaturated hydrocarbons is more typically a dark cloud characteristic, recent observations (Sakai et al., 2008, 2009) have identified carbon chain-rich protostars. The authors of that study ascribe the presence of these carbon chains to a gas-phase ion-molecule chemistry which occurs during and after the evaporation of methane from warming dust grains. In order to assess whether carbon chain inheritance or in situ production is

Figure 4.3: Column density ratios of CCS versus HC_3N (left) and HC_5N (right) compared to those found in cold clouds by Suzuki et al. (1992). The blue solid line represents the typical ratios of ~ 0.7 and ~ 2.0 noted in Suzuki et al. (1992) while the dashed blue lines show the typical 1σ spread. The dash-dot blue line indicates the maximum cold cloud ratio observed in Suzuki et al. (1992). In the right panel, the ratio for HC_5N is calculated with a rotational temperature of 42 K, shown in black circles, and of 13 K, shown in red stars. Source L1448 IRS is shown as a gray diamond since CCS, HC_3H , and HC_5N were not detected toward this protostar.

more common in protostars, we investigate whether WCCC characteristics can be found in the protostars in our sample. By searching for additional WCCC sources, or the presence of similar chemical trends, we can determine if WCCC is likely to be universal across protostars as a natural evolutionary stage, or if it represents a special case found only in specific physical protostellar conditions.

We compare our beam-averaged carbon chain abundances with observed abundances in WCCC sources to investigate the underlying carbon chain chemistry occurring in our unbiased sample. Although, we restrict our comparisons to low-mass sources, recent observations by Saul et al. (2015) have also identified evidence for WCCC in massive star-forming region NGC 3576. Observational data are taken from Hassel et al. (2008, 2011, and see references therein) for WCCC sources L1527 and B228. As the initial observations were reported in

Figure 4.4: Observed fractional abundances compared with observations of two WCCC sources. Left) Median fractional abundances are represented by upward red triangles and error bars span the first and third quartiles determined by survival analysis. Individual sources are represented with gray circles for detections and downward triangles for upper limits. Right) Same as the left plot but the individual sources have been assigned a color gradient corresponding to their CS fractional abundances for the sake of visual comparison.

terms of column densities, Hassel et al. (2011) assumed a total hydrogen column density of $N_H = 6 \times 10^{22} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ to convert to fractional abundances. This value is low compared to our typical $N_H \approx 1 \times 10^{24} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ by more than an order of magnitude. Also, observational coverage is not uniform. L1527 is lacking an observed fractional abundance for CCCS and B228 only has values for HC_5N and C_4H .

Figure 4.4 shows a comparison of our observations with known WCCC sources. The medians for all molecules in our sample are underabundant relative to the WCCC observations by at least two orders of magnitude. As shown by the individual protostellar abundances, there is significant scatter in carbon chain abundances among molecular families and individual protostars. L1455 IRS3 typically possesses the highest abundances for most molecules, and L1448 IRS1 is an outlier with only a detection of CS. L1455 IRS3 has a CCS abundance which is potentially consistent with that of L1527. No other sources in our sample come close to the carbon chain abundances observed in WCCCs.

Since we have adopted a different approach for determining abundances than Hassel et al. (2008, 2011), it is possible that abundances have not been derived consistently between our sample and theirs. To mitigate this concern, Figure 4.5 shows the same comparison but with column densities instead of fractional abundances. By using strict column densities, we are removing the effect of the choice of a lower value of N_H used to determine the L1527 and B228 fractional abundances. The same trends are evident as in the fractional abundance plots. However, in terms of column densities, several sources now exhibit CS and CCS column densities that are consistent or in excess of those reported for lukewarm corino L1527. Moreover, the observed column densities are typically only underabundant by an order of magnitude and with the exception of HC_5N , exhibit the same chemical relationships among species as the WCCC sources. This is potentially suggestive of a “scaled-down” WCCC, which would indicate that WCCC may be a universal phase in protostellar evolution, but that it happens with smaller abundances rather than the relatively large abundances currently reported for identified WCCC sources. However, since we do not identify any chemical relationships particular to WCCC sources, the carbon chains observed in our protostellar sample could also be the result of inheritance.

Next, we compare our observational data against the model expectations of Hassel et al. (2008, 2011). The chemical evolutionary models utilize the Ohio State University gas-grain code (Hasegawa et al., 1992) with additional modifications and improvements. The dust and gas temperatures are assumed to be in equilibrium throughout and the model is run separately for the cold prestellar core phase $T = 10$ K and warm-up scenarios with maximum temperatures of $T = 30, 100, 200$ K. The model expectations shown in Figure 4.6 are those taken from the latest and most comprehensive warm-up models of Hassel et al. (2011). The model fractional abundance for CCCS was provided by Hassel (private communication).

Most of the protostars in our sample have fractional abundances lower than the cold cloud $T = 10$ K model predictions. L1455 IRS3 has an HC_3N abundance in excess of the

Figure 4.5: Observed column densities compared with observations of two WCCC sources. Left) Median column densities are represented by upward red triangles and error bars span the first and third quartiles determined by survival analysis. Individual sources are represented with gray circles for detections and downward triangles for upper limits. Right) Same as the left plot but the individual sources have been assigned a color gradient corresponding to their CS column densities for the sake of visual comparison.

Figure 4.6: Observed fractional abundances compared with various model expectations. Left) Median fractional abundances are represented by upward red triangles and error bars span the first and third quartiles determined by survival analysis. Individual sources are represented with gray circles for detections and downward triangles for upper limits. Right) Same as the left plot but the individual sources have been assigned a color gradient corresponding to their CS fractional abundances for the sake of visual comparison.

10 K expectation, while L1455 IRS3 and IRAS 03254 exceed the cold cloud expectation for C_4H . IRAS 03254 also shows an elevated HC_5N abundance relative to the $T = 10$ K expectation. No sources in our sample are consistent with a temperature of 30 K, which is that of WCCC sources, or the hot corino warm-up model expectations. Similar to comparisons with WCCC sources, we find that our abundances across molecules demonstrate similar trends which appear to be scaled-down from the model expectations. This would imply that the chemistry of WCCC is not fundamentally different from the chemistry we observe toward these protostars and that other physical parameters, such as differing temperature regimes, are responsible for the observed underabundances. However, as noted above, we are unable to rule out chemical inheritance as the origin for the observed carbon chains.

Chapter 5

Conclusions

Based on a survey of carbon chain molecules toward 16 young low-mass protostars using the IRAM 30 m telescope, we conclude the following:

1. Pure carbon chains, as well as nitrogen- and sulfur-bearing carbon chains, are found to be common at this stage (Class 0/I) of protostellar evolution. Specifically, we detect CCS, CCCS, HC₃N, HC₅N, C₃H, and C₄H with detection fractions of 94%, 44%, 81%, 38%, 88%, and 88%, respectively. CCS, HC₃N, and C₄H are found to be particularly abundant in this sample with column densities in excess of $2 \times 10^{12} \text{ cm}^{-2}$.
2. The carbon chain median abundance is observed to decrease with chain size for sulfur and nitrogen containing carbon chains as expected. In contrast, for the pure carbon chains C_nH, an increase of one carbon from C₃H to C₄H leads to a two order of magnitude increase in median column density. This finding is not unexpected since unsaturated carbon chains with odd and even numbers of carbon atoms form via different production pathways.
3. Carbon chain column densities span at least an order of magnitude, often two orders. The distributions of carbon chains are quite broad, indicating considerable chemistry variation between the different sources.

4. With the exception of CCS and HC₃N, we find no significant correlations between molecules in different carbon chain families, a finding that implies that several independent carbon chain pathways may be operative. This correlation supports the notion that the production chemistry of C_nS and the cyanopolyynes are not just closely related in cold clouds but continue to be related in low-mass star formation.
5. Carbon chain abundances for all sources in our sample are underabundant, often by several orders of magnitude, relative to those reported for well-studied cold cloud TMC -1. Compared to two well-known WCCC sources and warm-up model expectations, we also find that most molecules and sources are underabundant, although by lesser fractions than relative to TMC-1. We do not identify any new WCCC sources in our sample and are unable to conclusively rule out either inheritance or “scaled-down” WCCC as the origin of the observed carbon chains.

Appendix A

Additional Information

A.1 Source Descriptions

A.1.1 B1-a, B1-c

Barnard 1 (B1) is a dense core which lies on the eastern rim of a $\sim 1^\circ$ diameter cavity in the Perseus molecular cloud complex (Walawender et al., 2005). B1 has been well studied in molecular line radio maps (e.g. Bachiller and Cernicharo, 1984; Ungerechts and Thaddeus, 1987; Bachiller et al., 1990) and is one of the few dark clouds with a measurement of its magnetic field (Goodman et al., 1989). The cloud core is roughly $2 \times 5 \text{ pc}^2$ in size and has a mass of approximately $1200 M_\odot$ (Walawender et al., 2005). There are four protostellar clumps in the core of B1 (B1-a, B1-b, B1-c, and B1-d), which are bright at both $24 \mu\text{m}$ and 1.1 mm (Enoch et al., 2006).

B1-a, which is associated with IRAS 03301+3057, powers a string of H_2 outflow knots to its west (Walawender et al., 2005). Hirano et al. (1997) detected a high-velocity CO outflow from the IRAS 03301+3057 source, which they concluded was an outflow seen pole-on; however, this outflow was not seen in subsequent observations by Walawender et al. (2005). The $12\text{-}100 \mu\text{m}$ slope of IRAS 03301+3057 is consistent with a Class I source (Walawender et al., 2005).

Identified as a star-forming core by Matthews and Wilson (2002) in SCUBA polarization measurements, B1-c powers a bright bipolar molecular outflow and jet and has no IRAS counterpart, suggesting that it may be a very young, deeply embedded protostar (Walawender et al., 2005). It is the brightest core in dust emission in B1 at submillimeter wavelengths and exhibits an atypical polarization signature, in which the polarized intensity rises continuously to the intensity peak (Matthews and Wilson, 2002). Each lobe of its outflow extends $\sim 200''$ to either side of the detected submillimeter clump. Assuming a 100 km s^{-1} outflow velocity, this gives a dynamic age of the flow of about 3000 yr, which is consistent with its characterization as a young Class 0 source (Walawender et al., 2005). Evidence for core rotation with its rotation axis aligned with its molecular outflow has also been reported in N_2H^+ observations (Matthews and Wilson, 2002).

A.1.2 HH 300

Originally discovered in the optical by Reipurth et al. (1997), the giant Herbig-Haro flow HH 300 is located in the westernmost region of the B18 molecular cloud (B18w) in the Taurus cloud complex (Arce and Goodman, 2001). B18w is a $1.7 \text{ pc} \times 0.7 \text{ pc}$ filamentary protuberance from the main B18 cloud. The source of HH 300 was established to be IRAS 04239+2436, which lies at the northern end of B18w, just west of the “bridge” between B18 and B18w (Reipurth et al., 1997). Near- and mid-infrared photometry (Myers et al., 1987) and its infrared spectrum (Greene and Lada, 1996) indicate that this is a $1.3 L_{\odot}$ class I young stellar object. The HH 300 flow consists of three redshifted HH objects (HH 300A, 300B, 300C), each with a bow shock-like morphology, close together at a distance of about 1.1 pc southwest of the outflow source, and a small blueshifted knot (HH 300D) about 0.02 pc northeast of the source (Arce and Goodman, 2001). Infrared camera multiobject spectrograph images by Reipurth et al. (2000) reveal a cometary nebula surrounding the

source, a jet on the blueshifted side of the HH flow along the symmetry axis of the nebula, and that IRAS 04239+2436 is a binary. A VLA detection of a radio source within the IRAS error ellipsoid has also been reported by Rodríguez and Reipurth (1998). Based on CO molecular-line maps, Arce and Goodman (2001) note that HH 300 has a clumpy structure arising from the prompt entrainment of ambient gas. Further, they conclude that HH 300 is a precessing and episodic outflow. Additionally, their $^{13}\text{CO}(1-0)$ observations show that the HH 300 flow has been able to redistribute considerable amounts of its surrounding medium-density ($\sim 10^3 \text{ cm}^{-3}$) gas.

A.1.3 B5 IRS1

B5 IRS1 (IRAS 03442+3242) is the brightest and best studied of four IRAS point sources in the Barnard 5 dark cloud (Beichman et al., 1984). Its spectral energy distribution is that of a Class I YSO (Lada, 1991) and it coincides with the peak molecular gas column density in the cloud, as traced by the low-level inversion transitions of ammonia (Benson et al., 1984). B5 IRS1 is thought to be a reddened YSO, likely a very young T Tauri star, embedded within its associated dense molecular cloud core (Myers et al., 1987). It is a source of Br α line emission associated with an energetic stellar wind (Smith et al., 1987) and has a collimated molecular outflow (Fuller et al., 1991). Moore and Emerson (1992, 1994) presented and discussed near-infrared polarimetric images of the faint reflection nebula associated with the outflow cavity and further showed that the source is fading with time at near-infrared wavelengths at an average rate of about 0.24 mag per year.

A.1.4 L1014 IRS

Using *Spitzer Space Telescope* observations of Bok globule L1014, previously classified as starless (Parker, 1988), Young et al. (2004) discovered an infrared point source with protostellar colors, L1014 IRS, located near the globule’s dust emission peak. High-resolution

molecular observations with SMA indicate that the protostar is not at the peak of the molecular and dust column density in the core, but offset by about $8''$ in the plane of the sky (Bourke et al., 2005). This offset is also seen in the (sub)millimeter continuum maps (Young et al., 2004) and the near-infrared extinction map (Huard et al., 2006). The infrared spectrum of L1014 IRS was consistent with (1) a protostar or proto-brown dwarf in L1014 at ~ 200 pc (Leung et al., 1982) or (2) an intermediate-mass T Tauri star ($L \sim 16 L_{\odot}$) associated with a background cloud in the Perseus arm at 2.6 kpc (Bourke et al., 2005). Assuming that the distance to L1014 IRS is 200 pc, the bolometric luminosity, assuming isotropic emission, is $\sim 0.09 L_{\odot}$ and the best fit to the spectral energy distribution is with a protostar luminosity of $0.025 L_{\odot}$ (Bourke et al., 2005). If L1014 IRS has the age of a typical Class I protostar of $\sim 10^5$ yr, then it has substellar mass of only $20M_{\text{Jup}} - 45M_{\text{Jup}}$ (Huard et al., 2006). However, no spectroscopic observations exist to determine its mass and accretion rate, and so it is unclear whether L1014 IRS is a young protostar still acquiring a significant fraction of its final mass or whether it is destined to remain substellar. Although recent VLA observations at 6 and 3.6 cm suggest that L1014 IRS is not an extremely young protostar but is a low-luminosity source that appears to have been accreting for at least several thousand years and is currently in a low accretion state (Shirley et al., 2007).

Prior observations strongly supported the conclusion that L1014 IRS is embedded within L1014 (Crapsi et al., 2005; Huard et al., 2006) and with the discovery of a low-mass ($< 10^{-4} M_{\odot}$), small (~ 500 AU) bipolar molecular outflow from L1014 IRS using the SMA, (Bourke et al., 2005) confirmed its association with the L1014 dense core. This makes L1014 IRS the lowest luminosity, and potentially the lowest mass, source known to be driving a bipolar molecular outflow.

A.1.5 IRAS 23238+7410

The CB244 source is a Bok globule at a distance of ~ 200 pc (Hilton and Lahulla, 1995) with an approximate extent of $\sim 6'$, or about 0.5 pc. The CB244 globule contains two submillimeter peaks, one associated with a Class 0 protostar known as IRAS 23238+7401, and one associated with a starless core at RA= $23^h25^m27.1^s$, Dec= $+74^h18'25.3''$. The IRAS 23238+7401 protostar also drives a molecular outflow (Clemens et al., 1991). Using recent *Herschel* observations along with previous (sub)millimeter and infrared data, Stutz et al. (2010) find the column-averaged dust-temperature near the protostar to be ~ 17.7 K and a total hydrogen mass of CB244 of $15 \pm 5 M_{\odot}$. The mass of the protostellar core was determined to be $1.6 \pm 0.1 M_{\odot}$ by integrating an ellipse with a mean radius of 10,000 AU around the protostar core.

A.1.6 L1489 IRS

L1489 IRS (IRAS 04016+2610) is a Class I protostar associated with a faint molecular outflow along the north-south direction on thousands of AU scale as observed by the JCMT in the $^{12}\text{CO}(3-2)$ line (Hogerheijde et al., 1998). Single-dish continuum observations at 1.3mm show that L1489 IRS is surrounded by a compact protostellar envelope with a size of $\sim 30''$ (~ 4200 AU) (Motte and André, 2001). Interferometric observations in millimeter molecular lines by Hogerheijde (2001) show that both infalling and rotational motions are present in the envelope on a 2000 AU scale with the rotational motion more dominant than the infalling motion. Both SMA millimeter continuum and HCO^+ (3-2) line emission observations (Brinch et al., 2007) and 1.3 mm continuum CARMA observations at subarcsecond resolution (Eisner, 2012) have revealed the presence of a $0.004 - 0.005 M_{\odot}$ Keplerian disk of radius $\approx 200 - 450$ AU embedded in the envelope as well as a protostar with mass $1.4 - 1.8 M_{\odot}$ depending on the assumption of $40 - 50^\circ$ inclination angle to the disk (Yen et al., 2013). Recent ALMA

1.3 mm continuum and molecular line observations suggest an outer disk radius of ~ 700 AU and mass of $\sim 0.005 M_{\odot}$. The protostellar mass is estimated to be $1.6 M_{\odot}$ with an inclination angle of 66° and the mass infalling rate is estimated to be $\sim 5 \times 10^{-7} M_{\odot} \text{ yr}^{-1}$.

A.1.7 IRAS 04108+2803

IRAS 04108+2803 is a $22''$ separation binary system in the L1495 region of Taurus (Duchêne et al., 2004) and IRAS 04108+2803B is the component that is less environmentally evolved based on its SED, emitting the majority of the far-IR emission from the system (Eisner et al., 2005). Previous models of this object include an infalling envelope (Kenyon et al., 1993; Whitney et al., 1997), a flared disk (Chiang and Goldreich, 1999), and a T Tauri star in a disk that has been dynamically warped by a hypothetical stellar companion (Terquem and Bertout, 1996). More recent modeling by Eisner et al. (2005) found that the system is best fit with a model incorporating a massive disk in addition to an envelope. This model implies an inclination of $i = 24^{\circ}$, a mass infall rate of $5 \times 10^{-6} M_{\odot} \text{ yr}^{-1}$, and a central luminosity ($L \approx 0.4 L_{\odot}$) typical of a Tauri star. This source is likely extremely disk-dominated (Eisner et al., 2005) but requires a massive envelope component to fit imaging and SED data along with *Spitzer* observations of $15.2 \mu\text{m}$ CO₂ ice absorption, attributed to a cold envelope (Watson et al., 2004).

A.1.8 IRAS 03245+3002, L1455 IRS3, L1455 SMM1

The L1455 region (Lynds, 1962) is located in the southwestern region of the Perseus molecular cloud about $40'$ southeast of L1448 (Bally et al., 1997) and encloses an area of about 7.6 pc^2 (Chou et al., 2016). L1455 is an intermediate mass cloud which contains a complex CO outflow (Juan et al., 1993) as well as numerous HH objects (Bally et al., 1997; Chou et al., 2016). It contains 11 YSOs with the majority of them being in their early stages

(Class 0/I) (Young et al., 2015). The first three protostars discovered in the IRAS catalogs were L1455 IRS1, L1455 IRS2, and L1455 IRS3 in the central region of L1455 (Bachiller and Cernicharo, 1986; Helou and Walker, 1988) with additional sources being found in the proximity of them. Particularly, Jørgensen et al. (2006) identify L1455 IRS4, L1455 IRS5, and L1455 IRS6, which are all clustered inside a small $\sim 1 \text{ pc}^2$ region (Chou et al., 2016).

L1455 IRS3 (IRAS 03249+2957) is a faint source that was detected at $60 \mu\text{m}$ by Bachiller and Cernicharo (1986) and is likely a Class I object (Enoch et al., 2009). L1455 SMM1 (L1455 IRS4) is a Class 0 object (Enoch et al., 2009), associated with the strongest dust continuum peaks in maps of submillimeter emission (Jørgensen et al., 2006). Some authors ascribe the origin of the observed dominant northwest-to-southeast elongated outflow, which overlaps a smaller one perpendicular to it (Davis et al., 1997) to L1455 SMM1, which sits approximately in the center of the outflow (Jørgensen et al., 2006; Simon, 2009; Arce et al., 2010). Chou et al. (2016) identify a protostellar core in the location of L1455 SMM1 in $\text{C}^{18}\text{O}(2-1)$ emission with a velocity component around $v \sim 4.8 \text{ km s}^{-1}$.

Juan et al. (1993) identify IRAS 03245+3002 (L1455 IRS1) as the driving source of this second, perpendicular outflow mentioned above. A recent CARMA survey has verified this, though with a slightly different outflow axis position angle (Hull et al., 2014). IRAS 03245+3002 is a Class 0/I source (Young et al., 2015) and recent SMA and IRAM 30m observations by Chou et al. (2016) suggest the presence of a Keplerian disk with a radius $< 200 \text{ AU}$ around IRAS 03245+3002 with a protostellar mass of about $0.28 M_{\odot}$ and faster-than-average core rotation. These observations also show IRAS 03245+3002 is located in a dense 0.05 pc core with a mass of $0.54 M_{\odot}$, connecting to a filamentary structure.

A.1.9 SVS 4-5

SVS 4 is a small but dense cluster of low- to intermediate-mass pre-main sequence stars located in the south-eastern core of the Serpens molecular cloud (Pontoppidan et al., 2004). It was first studied by Eiroa and Casali (1989), who found it to be one of the densest YSO clusters known with 11 stars within a region only 12000 AU across. SVS 4-5, which has a stellar mass of $3.5 M_{\odot}$, is known to trace the envelope of the foreground Class 0 object SMM 4 (Pontoppidan et al., 2004). An enhanced CH_3OH abundance is also detected toward SVS 4-5 (Boogert et al., 2008).

A.1.10 L1448 IRS1

L1448 is a dark cloud located approximately 1° southwest from NGC 1333 in the Perseus cloud complex (Bachiller and Cernicharo, 1986). Three infrared sources were observed by IRAS and were denoted IRS1, IRS2, and IRS3 by Bachiller and Cernicharo (1986). L1448 IRS1 exhibits strong $\text{H}\alpha$ emission and its position corresponds to that of the red and nebulous object RNO 13 in the list of Cohen (1980). L1448 IRS1 is associated with an HH object (HH194 in Davis et al., 2008). This source was not catalogued as a YSO by Jørgensen et al. (2006) and was only detected in the *Spitzer* MIPS 1 band in the *c2d* catalog, being classified as ‘star + dust.’ The lack of a detection in the IRAC bands is likely due to saturation as L1448 IRS1 is quite bright (Davis et al., 2008).

A.1.11 IRAS 03235+3004, IRAS 03254+3050, IRAS 03271+3013

IRAS 03254+3050 and IRAS 03271+3013 are Class 0/I objects (Enoch et al., 2009; Young et al., 2015) associated with NGC 1333 in Perseus. NGC 1333 is currently the most active region of star formation in the Perseus molecular cloud and is located at the northern end of a degree-long, north-south ridge of CO emission at the west side of a large cavity in Perseus

(Walawender et al., 2008). IRAS 03235+3004 is a Class 0 object (Enoch et al., 2009) located to the west of L1455 in Perseus (Chou et al., 2016).

A.2 Complete Spectral Data

Figures A.1-A.6 show the complete spectral data used to derive rotational temperatures and column densities. Spectra of C₄H are found in Figure 2 in Graninger et al. (2016).

A.3 Integrated Line Intensities

Tables A.1-A.6 present the integrated intensity measurements from Gaussian fits to detected molecular lines. The data from these tables were used to determine rotational diagrams for molecules with sufficient line detections.

A.4 Rotational Diagrams

Figures A.7-A.9 show rotational diagrams for each source and each molecule that were used to derive rotational temperatures.

A.5 Correlation Coefficients and Alternative Column Densities for HC₅N

Here, we provide more information relevant to our analysis, including additional molecule-to-molecule correlation coefficients (Tables A.7 and A.8) and HC₅N column densities derived via $T_{\text{rot}} = 13 \text{ K}$ (Table A.9).

Figure A.1: Zoomed-in spectra of CS toward the low-mass YSO sample. Rest frequencies derived assuming the characteristic velocity of each source.

Figure A.2: Zoomed-in spectra of CCCS toward the low-mass YSO sample. Rest frequencies derived assuming the characteristic velocity of each source.

Figure A.3: Zoomed-in spectra of HC_3N toward the low-mass YSO sample. Rest frequencies derived assuming the characteristic velocity of each source.

Figure A.4: Zoomed-in spectra of C_3H toward the low-mass YSO sample. Rest frequencies derived assuming the characteristic velocity of each source.

Figure A.5: Zoomed-in spectra of HC_5N toward the low-mass YSO sample. Rest frequencies derived assuming the characteristic velocity of each source. Individual line detections are highlighted with red stars.

Figure A.6: (continued) Zoomed-in spectra of HC_5N toward the low-mass YSO sample. Rest frequencies derived assuming the characteristic velocity of each source. Individual line detections are highlighted with red stars.

Table A.1: Integrated CS Intensities in K km s⁻¹

Source	96.413 GHz $J = 2 - 1$	97.172 GHz $J = 2 - 1$	97.981 GHz $J = 2 - 1$
B1-a	1.158 [0.008]	0.194 [0.008]	6.355 [0.012]
SVS 4-5	1.579 [0.007]	0.188 [0.006]	13.62 [0.032]
B1-c*	0.406 [0.004]	0.074 [0.005]	2.572 [0.032]
IRAS 23238+7401	0.241 [0.002]	0.045 [0.003]	2.407 [0.005]
L1455 IRS3	0.134 [0.003]	0.025 [0.003]	1.116 [0.003]
B5 IRS 1	0.285 [0.008]	0.041 [0.006]	2.199 [0.008]
L1455 SMM1	0.436 [0.003]	0.063 [0.003]	2.951 [0.009]
IRAS 03245+3002	0.463 [0.004]	0.060 [0.004]	4.283 [0.008]
L1014 IRS	0.093 [0.002]	0.012 [0.002]	0.729 [0.002]
IRAS 04108+2803	0.132 [0.004]	0.023 [0.003]	0.658 [0.003]
IRAS 03235+3004	0.195 [0.005]	0.021 [0.003]	1.151 [0.010]
L1489 IRS	0.082 [0.006]	0.016 [0.004]	1.526 [0.003]
HH 300	0.143 [0.007]	0.029 [0.006]	0.745 [0.013]
IRAS 03271+3013	0.037 [0.003]	<0.007	0.758 [0.003]
IRAS 03254+3050*	0.025 [0.003]	<0.010	0.454 [0.005]
L1448 IRS1*	0.028 [0.002]	0.019 [0.002]	0.535 [0.003]

*B1-c shows weak self-absorption to the right side of lines, IRAS 03254+3050 shows significant self-absorption to the left of lines, and L1448 IRS1 shows weak self-absorption to the right of lines.

Table A.2: Integrated CCS Intensities in K km s⁻¹

Source	93.870 GHz $J_N = 8_7 - 7_6$	99.867 GHz $J_N = 7_8 - 6_7$	113.410 GHz $J_N = 8_9 - 7_8$
B1-a	0.476 [0.005]	0.193 [0.004]	0.142 [0.007]
SVS 4-5	0.312 [0.005]	0.111 [0.002]	0.106 [0.005]
B1-c	0.321 [0.005]	0.084 [0.003]	0.056 [0.010]
IRAS 23238+7401	0.103 [0.002]	0.032 [0.002]	<0.023
L1455 IRS3	0.103 [0.004]	0.036 [0.003]	<0.022
B5 IRS 1	0.145 [0.008]	0.068 [0.005]	0.050 [0.012]
L1455 SMM1	0.338 [0.004]	0.114 [0.003]	0.095 [0.006]
IRAS 03245+3002	0.309 [0.005]	0.132 [0.003]	0.121 [0.005]
L1014 IRS	0.076 [0.003]	0.017[0.003]	<0.014
IRAS 04108+2803	0.046 [0.004]	<0.010	<0.020
IRAS 03235+3004	0.174 [0.005]	0.053 [0.003]	0.050 [0.007]
L1489 IRS	0.029 [0.007]	0.019 [0.004]	<0.027
HH 300	0.066 [0.006]	0.018 [0.003]	0.013 [0.009]
IRAS 03271+3013	0.023 [0.004]	<0.007	<0.018
IRAS 03254+3050	0.017 [0.004]	<0.012	<0.025
L1448 IRS1	<0.014	<0.008	<0.017

Table A.3: Integrated CCCS Intensities in K km s⁻¹

Source	98.269 GHz $J = 17 - 16$	109.828 GHz $J = 19 - 18$
B1-a	0.046 [0.002]	0.030 [0.005]
SVS 4-5	0.069 [0.003]	0.038 [0.003]
B1-c	0.040 [0.004]	0.019 [0.003]
IRAS 23238+7401	0.012 [0.003]	<0.006
L1455 IRS3	<0.009	<0.014
B5 IRS 1	<0.014	<0.023
L1455 SMM1	0.028 [0.003]	0.026 [0.003]
IRAS 03245+3002	0.065 [0.003]	0.045 [0.003]
L1014 IRS	<0.008	<0.009
IRAS 04108+2803	<0.012	<0.010
IRAS 03235+3004	0.015 [0.003]	<0.011
L1489 IRS	<0.009	<0.014
HH 300	<0.013	<0.022
IRAS 03271+3013	<0.009	<0.010
IRAS 03254+3050	<0.012	<0.011
L1448 IRS1	<0.008	<0.012

Table A.4: Integrated HC₃N Intensities in K km s⁻¹

Source	100.076 GHz $J = 11 - 10$	109.174 GHz $J = 12 - 11$
B1-a	0.615 [0.004]	0.474 [0.003]
SVS 4-5	1.823 [0.007]	1.475 [0.008]
B1-c	...	0.621 [0.005]
IRAS 23238+7401	...	0.471 [0.003]
L1455 IRS3	...	0.097 [0.004]
B5 IRS 1	0.448 [0.005]	0.337 [0.007]
L1455 SMM1	...	0.357 [0.002]
IRAS 03245+3002	...	0.531 [0.002]
L1014 IRS	...	0.065 [0.003]
IRAS 04108+2803	<0.012	<0.008
IRAS 03235+3004	0.649 [0.003]	0.526 [0.003]
L1489 IRS	0.084 [0.005]	0.074 [0.006]
HH 300	...	<0.018
IRAS 03271+3013	...	0.253 [0.004]
IRAS 03254+3050	...	<0.012
L1448 IRS1	...	<0.009

Note: Dots (...) indicate that the 100.076 GHz transition was not contained in the spectral window for that particular source.

 Table A.5: Integrated HC₅N Intensities in K km s⁻¹

Source	93.188 GHz $J = 35 - 34$	95.850 GHz $J = 36 - 35$	98.513 GHz $J = 37 - 36$	109.161 GHz $J = 41 - 40$	111.823 GHz $J = 42 - 41$	114.485 GHz $J = 43 - 42$
B1-a	<0.012	<0.015	0.009 [0.003]	<0.010	<0.013	<0.030
SVS 4-5	0.019 [0.005]	0.023 [0.005]	0.024 [0.002]	0.014 [0.004]	<0.009	<0.022
B1-c	0.017 [0.004]	<0.014	<0.009	<0.015	<0.019	0.033 [0.011]
IRAS 23238+7401	<0.012	0.016 [0.003]	0.014 [0.002]	<0.010	<0.009	<0.021
L1455 IRS3	<0.012	<0.014	<0.010	<0.011	<0.012	<0.024
B5 IRS 1	<0.031	<0.023	0.012 [0.005]	0.024 [0.006]	<0.027	<0.052
L1455 SMM1	<0.014	<0.014	<0.010	<0.012	<0.013	<0.022
IRAS 03245+3002	0.011 [0.005]	<0.011	<0.009	0.012 [0.004]	<0.014	0.012 [0.003]
L1014 IRS	<0.011	<0.010	<0.006	<0.009	<0.012	<0.022
IRAS 04108+2803	<0.016	<0.014	<0.009	<0.013	<0.012	<0.028
IRAS 03235+3004	<0.017	<0.017	<0.010	<0.012	<0.012	<0.023
L1489 IRS	<0.020	<0.022	<0.016	<0.015	<0.021	<0.029
HH 300	<0.016	<0.015	<0.013	<0.018	<0.020	<0.026
IRAS 03271+3013	<0.014	<0.012	<0.010	<0.011	<0.016	<0.031
IRAS 03254+3050	<0.015	<0.014	0.015 [0.003]	0.009 [0.003]	<0.016	<0.025
L1448 IRS1	<0.009	<0.012	<0.010	<0.009	<0.014	<0.024

Table A.6: Integrated C₃H Intensities in K km s⁻¹

Source	97.995 GHz	97.996 GHz	98.012 GHz	98.013 GHz
	$F = 5 - 4, l = e$	$F = 4 - 3, l = e$	$F = 5 - 4, l = f$	$F = 4 - 3, l = f$
B1-a	0.032 [0.003]	0.028 [0.003]	0.025 [0.003]	0.033 [0.003]
SVS 4-5	0.036 [0.003]	0.035 [0.005]	0.027 [0.002]	0.027 [0.003]
B1-c	0.033 [0.003]	0.033 [0.004]	0.026 [0.004]	0.036 [0.003]
IRAS 23238+7401	0.021 [0.002]	0.017 [0.004]	0.020 [0.002]	0.008 [0.002]
L1455 IRS3	0.017 [0.003]	0.016 [0.002]	0.022 [0.003]	0.021 [0.003]
B5 IRS 1	0.041 [0.005]	0.030 [0.005]	0.031 [0.006]	0.020 [0.006]
L1455 SMM1	0.034 [0.004]	0.016 [0.003]	0.038 [0.004]	0.020 [0.003]
IRAS 03245+3002	0.007 [0.002]	0.009 [0.003]	0.026 [0.003]	0.012 [0.002]
L1014 IRS	0.010 [0.002]	0.028 [0.003]	0.011 [0.001]	0.009 [0.003]
IRAS 04108+2803	<0.009	<0.009	0.017 [0.003]	0.011 [0.005]
IRAS 03235+3004	0.049 [0.004]	0.034 [0.002]	0.037 [0.004]	0.046 [0.003]
L1489 IRS	<0.011	<0.011	<0.013	<0.013
HH 300	0.010 [0.004]	<0.014	0.012 [0.004]	<0.012
IRAS 03271+3013	0.037 [0.003]	<0.012	<0.008	<0.009
IRAS 03254+3050	<0.012	<0.012	0.016 [0.003]	<0.012
L1448 IRS1	<0.009	<0.009	<0.007	<0.007

Note: All transitions are $J = \frac{9}{2} - \frac{7}{2}$.

Figure A.7: Rotational diagrams for CCCS. The remaining sources have no line detections and are not shown.

Figure A.8: Rotational diagrams for HC_3N . The remaining sources have no line detections and are not shown.

Figure A.9: Rotational diagrams for HC_5N . The remaining sources have no line detections and are not shown.

Table A.7: Pearson Coefficients for Molecule-Molecule Correlations

	CS	CCS	CCCS	HC_3N	HC_5N	C_3H
C_4H	0.27 [14]	0.44 [15]	-0.16 [7]	0.06 [11]	0.54 [7]	0.66 [14]
C_3H	0.37 [14]	0.39 [15]	-0.05 [7]	0.34 [11]	0.47 [7]	
HC_5N	0.68 [7]	0.24 [7]	-0.16 [5]	0.12 [6]		
HC_3N	0.59 [12]	0.49 [13]	0.87 [7]			
CCCS	0.16 [7]	0.01 [7]				
CCS	0.71 [15]					

Note: Brackets indicate the number of sources with detections for both molecules.

Table A.8: Spearman Coefficients for Perseus-Only, Molecule-Molecule Correlations

	CS	CCS	CCCS	HC_3N	HC_5N	C_3H
C_4H	0.52 [9]	0.58 [9]	-0.50 [5]	0.57 [8]	0.60 [5]	0.69 [9]
C_3H	0.22 [9]	0.19 [9]	-0.50 [5]	0.19 [8]	0.60 [5]	
HC_5N	0.30 [5]	0.30 [5]	-0.50 [3]	0.20 [4]		
HC_3N	0.88 [8]	0.83 [8]	-0.10 [5]			
CCCS	-0.10 [5]	-0.50 [5]				
CCS	0.63 [9]					

Note: Brackets indicate the number of sources with detections for both molecules.

Table A.9: HC₅N Column Densities for 13 K

Source	N (cm ⁻²)
B1-a	4.7 [3.6] × 10 ¹²
SVS 4-5	4.3 [1.0] × 10 ¹³
B1-c	4.5 [3.3] × 10 ¹²
IRAS 23238+7401	6.3 [4.8] × 10 ¹²
L1455 IRS3	<2.0 × 10 ¹²
B5 IRS 1	2.6 [2.2] × 10 ¹³
L1455 SMM1	<4.8 × 10 ¹²
IRAS 03245+3002	3.0 [3.2] × 10 ¹³
L1014 IRS	<3.0 × 10 ¹²
IRAS 04108+2803	<4.4 × 10 ¹²
IRAS 03235+3004	<4.5 × 10 ¹²
L1489 IRS	<5.5 × 10 ¹²
HH 300	<4.3 × 10 ¹²
IRAS 03271+3013	<3.8 × 10 ¹²
IRAS 03254+3050	1.2 [1.0] × 10 ¹³
L1448 IRS1	<2.5 × 10 ¹²
Species Mean	1.8 [1.5] × 10 ¹³

Bibliography

- F. C. Adams, C. J. Lada, and F. H. Shu. Spectral evolution of young stellar objects. *The Astrophysical Journal*, 312:788–806, Jan. 1987. doi: 10.1086/164924.
- M. Agundez, J. Cernicharo, G. Quintana-Lacaci, A. Castro-Carrizo, L. Velilla Prieto, N. Marcelino, M. Guelin, C. Joblin, J. A. Martin-Gago, C. A. Gottlieb, N. A. Patel, and M. C. McCarthy. The growth of carbon chains in IRC+10216 mapped with ALMA. *ArXiv e-prints*, Feb. 2017.
- Y. Aikawa, N. Ohashi, S.-i. Inutsuka, E. Herbst, and S. Takakuwa. Molecular Evolution in Collapsing Prestellar Cores. *The Astrophysical Journal*, 552:639–653, May 2001. doi: 10.1086/320551.
- Y. Aikawa, V. Wakelam, F. Hersant, R. T. Garrod, and E. Herbst. From Prestellar to Protostellar Cores. II. Time Dependence and Deuterium Fractionation. *The Astrophysical Journal*, 760:40, Nov. 2012. doi: 10.1088/0004-637X/760/1/40.
- K. N. Allers, D. T. Jaffe, J. H. Lacy, B. T. Draine, and M. J. Richter. H₂ Pure Rotational Lines in the Orion Bar. *The Astrophysical Journal*, 630:368–380, Sept. 2005. doi: 10.1086/431919.
- P. N. Appleton, P. Guillard, A. Togi, K. Alatalo, F. Boulanger, M. Cluver, G. Pineau des Forêts, U. Lisenfeld, P. Ogle, and C. K. Xu. Powerful H₂ Line Cooling in Stephan’s Quintet. II. Group-wide Gas and Shock Modeling of the Warm H₂ and a Comparison with

- [C II] 157.7 μm Emission and Kinematics. *The Astrophysical Journal*, 836:76, Feb. 2017. doi: 10.3847/1538-4357/836/1/76.
- H. G. Arce and A. A. Goodman. The Episodic, Precessing Giant Molecular Outflow from IRAS 04239+2436 (HH 300). *The Astrophysical Journal*, 554:132–151, June 2001. doi: 10.1086/321334.
- H. G. Arce and A. I. Sargent. Pushing the Envelope: The Impact of an Outflow at the Earliest Stages of Star Formation. *The Astrophysical Journal*, 624:232–245, May 2005. doi: 10.1086/428934.
- H. G. Arce, J. Santiago-García, J. K. Jørgensen, M. Tafalla, and R. Bachiller. Complex Molecules in the L1157 Molecular Outflow. *The Astrophysical Journal, Letters*, 681:L21, July 2008. doi: 10.1086/590110.
- H. G. Arce, M. A. Borkin, A. A. Goodman, J. E. Pineda, and M. W. Halle. The complete survey of outflows in perseus. *The Astrophysical Journal*, 715(2):1170, 2010.
- Y. Aso, N. Ohashi, K. Saigo, S. Koyamatsu, Y. Aikawa, M. Hayashi, M. N. Machida, M. Saito, S. Takakuwa, K. Tomida, K. Tomisaka, and H.-W. Yen. ALMA Observations of the Transition from Infall Motion to Keplerian Rotation around the Late-phase Protostar TMC-1A. *The Astrophysical Journal*, 812:27, Oct. 2015. doi: 10.1088/0004-637X/812/1/27.
- R. Bachiller and J. Cernicharo. Molecular observations of B 1 - A dense globule in Perseus. *Astronomy and Astrophysics*, 140:414–420, Nov. 1984.
- R. Bachiller and J. Cernicharo. Physical and chemical conditions in Perseus globules from NH₃ and HC₃N observations. *Astronomy and Astrophysics*, 168:262–270, Nov. 1986.

- R. Bachiller, K. M. Menten, and S. del Rio Alvarez. Anatomy of a dark cloud - A multi-molecular study of Barnard 1. *Astronomy and Astrophysics*, 236:461–471, Sept. 1990.
- A. Bacmann, V. Taquet, A. Faure, C. Kahane, and C. Ceccarelli. Detection of complex organic molecules in a prestellar core: a new challenge for astrochemical models. *Astronomy and Astrophysics*, 541:L12, May 2012. doi: 10.1051/0004-6361/201219207.
- J. Bally, D. Devine, V. Alten, and R. S. Sutherland. New Herbig-Haro Flows in L1448 and L1455. *The Astrophysical Journal*, 478:603–613, Mar. 1997. doi: 10.1086/303802.
- N. Balucani, C. Ceccarelli, and V. Taquet. Formation of complex organic molecules in cold objects: the role of gas-phase reactions. *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomy Society*, 449:L16–L20, Apr. 2015. doi: 10.1093/mnrasl/slv009.
- D. R. Bates. Rate of $\text{CH}_3^+ + \text{H}_2$ yields $\text{CH}_5^+ + \text{HV}$ and role of electronic transitions in other radiative association processes. *The Astrophysical Journal*, 312:363–366, Jan. 1987. doi: 10.1086/164882.
- C. A. Beichman, R. E. Jennings, J. P. Emerson, B. Baud, S. Harris, M. Rowan-Robinson, H. H. Aumann, T. N. Gautier, F. C. Gillett, H. J. Habing, P. L. Marsden, G. Neugebauer, and E. Young. The formation of solar type stars - IRAS observations of the dark cloud Barnard 5. *The Astrophysical Journal, Letters*, 278:L45–L48, Mar. 1984. doi: 10.1086/184219.
- P. J. Benson, P. C. Myers, and E. L. Wright. Dense cores in dark clouds - Young embedded stars at 2 micrometers. *The Astrophysical Journal, Letters*, 279:L27–L30, Apr. 1984. doi: 10.1086/184248.
- E. A. Bergin and W. D. Langer. Chemical Evolution in Preprotostellar and Protostellar Cores. *The Astrophysical Journal*, 486:316–328, Sept. 1997. doi: 10.1086/304510.

- E. A. Bergin and M. Tafalla. Cold Dark Clouds: The Initial Conditions for Star Formation. *Annual Review of Astronomy and Astrophysics*, 45:339–396, Sept. 2007. doi: 10.1146/annurev.astro.45.071206.100404.
- J. B. Bergner, K. I. Öberg, G. R. T., and G. D. M. Complex Organic Molecules Towards Embedded Low-Mass Protostars. submitted.
- S. E. Bisschop, G. W. Fuchs, E. F. van Dishoeck, and H. Linnartz. H-atom bombardment of CO₂, HCOOH, and CH₃CHO containing ices. *Astronomy and Astrophysics*, 474:1061–1071, Nov. 2007a. doi: 10.1051/0004-6361:20078210.
- S. E. Bisschop, J. K. Jørgensen, E. F. van Dishoeck, and E. B. M. de Wachter. Testing grain-surface chemistry in massive hot-core regions. *Astronomy and Astrophysics*, 465: 913–929, Apr. 2007b. doi: 10.1051/0004-6361:20065963.
- G. A. Blake, E. C. Sutton, C. R. Masson, and T. G. Phillips. Molecular abundances in OMC-1 - The chemical composition of interstellar molecular clouds and the influence of massive star formation. *The Astrophysical Journal*, 315:621–645, Apr. 1987. doi: 10.1086/165165.
- A. C. A. Boogert. Telescope Observations of Interstellar and Circumstellar Ices: Successes of and Need for Laboratory Simulations. *IAU Focus Meeting*, 29(27):317–318, Oct. 2016. doi: 10.1017/S174392131600315X.
- A. C. A. Boogert, K. M. Pontoppidan, C. Knez, F. Lahuis, J. Kessler-Silacci, E. F. van Dishoeck, G. A. Blake, J.-C. Augereau, S. E. Bisschop, S. Bottinelli, T. Y. Brooke, J. Brown, A. Crapsi, N. J. Evans, II, H. J. Fraser, V. Geers, T. L. Huard, J. K. Jørgensen, K. I. Öberg, L. E. Allen, P. M. Harvey, D. W. Koerner, L. G. Mundy, D. L. Padgett, A. I. Sargent, and K. R. Stapelfeldt. The c2d Spitzer Spectroscopic Survey of Ices around Low-Mass Young Stellar Objects. I. H₂O and the 5-8 μ m Bands. *The Astrophysical Journal*, 678:985-1004, May 2008. doi: 10.1086/533425.

- S. Bottinelli, C. Ceccarelli, R. Neri, J. P. Williams, E. Caux, S. Cazaux, B. Lefloch, S. Maret, and A. G. G. M. Tielens. Near-Arcsecond Resolution Observations of the Hot Corino of the Solar-Type Protostar IRAS 16293-2422. *The Astrophysical Journal, Letters*, 617:L69–L72, Dec. 2004. doi: 10.1086/426964.
- S. Bottinelli, C. Ceccarelli, J. P. Williams, and B. Lefloch. Hot corinos in NGC 1333-IRAS4B and IRAS2A. *Astronomy and Astrophysics*, 463:601–610, Feb. 2007. doi: 10.1051/0004-6361:20065139.
- T. L. Bourke, A. Crapsi, P. C. Myers, N. J. Evans, II, D. J. Wilner, T. L. Huard, J. K. Jørgensen, and C. H. Young. Discovery of a Low-Mass Bipolar Molecular Outflow from L1014-IRS with the Submillimeter Array. *The Astrophysical Journal, Letters*, 633:L129–L132, Nov. 2005. doi: 10.1086/498449.
- C. Brinch, A. Crapsi, J. K. Jørgensen, M. R. Hogerheijde, and T. Hill. A deeply embedded young protoplanetary disk around L1489 IRS observed by the Submillimeter Array. *Astronomy and Astrophysics*, 475:915–923, Dec. 2007. doi: 10.1051/0004-6361:20078249.
- N. W. Broten, T. Oka, L. W. Avery, J. M. MacLeod, and H. W. Kroto. The detection of HC₉N in interstellar space. *The Astrophysical Journal, Letters*, 223:L105–L107, July 1978. doi: 10.1086/182739.
- J. Cami, J. Bernard-Salas, E. Peeters, and S. E. Malek. Detection of C₆₀ and C₇₀ in a Young Planetary Nebula. *Science*, 329:1180, Sept. 2010. doi: 10.1126/science.1192035.
- A. Canosa, A. Páramo, S. D. Le Picard, and I. R. Sims. An experimental study of the reaction kinetics of C₂(X ¹Σ_g⁺) with hydrocarbons (CH₄, C₂H₂, C₂H₄, C₂H₆ and C₃H₈) over the temperature range 24-300 K: Implications for the atmospheres of Titan and the Giant Planets. *Icarus*, 187:558–568, Apr. 2007. doi: 10.1016/j.icarus.2006.10.009.

- M. Carter, B. Lazareff, D. Maier, J.-Y. Chenu, A.-L. Fontana, Y. Bortolotti, C. Boucher, A. Navarrini, S. Blanchet, A. Greve, D. John, C. Kramer, F. Morel, S. Navarro, J. Peñalver, K. F. Schuster, and C. Thum. The EMIR multi-band mm-wave receiver for the IRAM 30-m telescope. *Astronomy and Astrophysics*, 538:A89, Feb. 2012. doi: 10.1051/0004-6361/201118452.
- S. Cazaux, A. G. G. M. Tielens, C. Ceccarelli, A. Castets, V. Wakelam, E. Caux, B. Parise, and D. Teyssier. The Hot Core around the Low-mass Protostar IRAS 16293-2422: Scoundrels Rule! *The Astrophysical Journal, Letters*, 593:L51–L55, Aug. 2003. doi: 10.1086/378038.
- C. Ceccarelli. Observations of Low-Mass Protostars: Cold Envelopes and Hot Corinos. In D. C. Lis, G. A. Blake, and E. Herbst, editors, *Astrochemistry: Recent Successes and Current Challenges*, volume 231 of *IAU Symposium*, pages 1–16, 2005. doi: 10.1017/S1743921306006995.
- J. Cernicharo. The Physical Conditions of Low Mass Star Forming Regions. In C. J. Lada and N. D. Kylafis, editors, *NATO Advanced Science Institutes (ASI) Series C*, volume 342 of *NATO Advanced Science Institutes (ASI) Series C*, page 287, 1991.
- J. Cernicharo, N. Marcelino, E. Roueff, M. Gerin, A. Jiménez-Escobar, and G. M. Muñoz Caro. Discovery of the Methoxy Radical, CH₃O, toward B1: Dust Grain and Gas-phase Chemistry in Cold Dark Clouds. *The Astrophysical Journal, Letters*, 759:L43, Nov. 2012. doi: 10.1088/2041-8205/759/2/L43.
- K. Cernis. Interstellar extinction in the direction of the open cluster IC 348 and the Per OB2 association. *Baltic Astronomy*, 2:214, Jan. 1993.
- D. Chastaing, P. L. James, I. R. Sims, and I. W. M. Smith. Neutral-neutral reactions at the temperatures of interstellar clouds. Rate coefficients for reactions of C₂H radicals

- with O₂, C₂H₂, C₂H₄ and C₃H₆ down to 15 K. *Faraday Discussions*, 109:165, 1998. doi: 10.1039/a800495a.
- D. Chastaing, S. D. Le Picard, I. R. Sims, and I. W. M. Smith. Rate coefficients for the reactions of C(³P_J) atoms with C₂H₂, C₂H₄, CH₃CCH and H₂CCCH₂ at temperatures down to 15 K. *Astronomy and Astrophysics*, 365:241–247, Jan. 2001. doi: 10.1051/0004-6361:20000026.
- E. I. Chiang and P. Goldreich. Spectral Energy Distributions of Passive T Tauri Disks: Inclination. *The Astrophysical Journal*, 519:279–284, July 1999. doi: 10.1086/307351.
- N. Choi, M. Blitz, K. McKee, M. Pilling, and P. Seakins. H atom branching ratios from the reactions of cn radicals with c₂h₂ and c₂h₄. *Chemical Physics Letters*, 384(13):68 – 72, 2004. ISSN 0009-2614. doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.cplett.2003.11.100>.
- H.-G. Chou, H.-W. Yen, P. M. Koch, and S. Guilloteau. Protostar l1455 irs1: A rotating disk connecting to a filamentary network. *The Astrophysical Journal*, 823(2):151, 2016.
- D. P. Clemens, J. L. Yun, and M. H. Heyer. BOK globules and small molecular clouds - Deep IRAS photometry and ¹²CO spectroscopy. *The Astrophysical Journal, Supplement*, 75:877–904, Mar. 1991. doi: 10.1086/191552.
- M. Cohen. Red and nebulous objects in dark clouds - A survey. *The Astronomical Journal*, 85:29–35, Jan. 1980. doi: 10.1086/112630.
- A. Crapsi, C. H. Devries, T. L. Huard, J.-E. Lee, P. C. Myers, N. A. Ridge, T. L. Bourke, N. J. Evans, II, J. K. Jørgensen, J. Kauffmann, C. W. Lee, Y. L. Shirley, and C. H. Young. Dynamical and chemical properties of the “starless” core L1014. *Astronomy and Astrophysics*, 439:1023–1032, Sept. 2005. doi: 10.1051/0004-6361:20042411.

- T. E. Cravens and A. Dalgarno. Ionization, dissociation, and heating efficiencies of cosmic rays in a gas of molecular hydrogen. *The Astrophysical Journal*, 219:750–752, Jan. 1978. doi: 10.1086/155833.
- J. Crovisier, D. Bockelée-Morvan, P. Colom, N. Biver, D. Despois, D. C. Lis, and Teamtarget-of-opportunity radio observations of comets. The composition of ices in comet C/1995 O1 (Hale-Bopp) from radio spectroscopy. Further results and upper limits on undetected species. *Astronomy and Astrophysics*, 418:1141–1157, May 2004. doi: 10.1051/0004-6361:20035688.
- C. J. Davis, T. P. Ray, J. Eisloffel, and D. Corcoran. Near-IR imaging of the molecular outflows in HH24-26, L1634(HH240-241), L1660(HH72) and RNO15FIR. *Astronomy and Astrophysics*, 324:263–275, Aug. 1997.
- C. J. Davis, P. Scholz, P. Lucas, M. D. Smith, and A. Adamson. A shallow though extensive H₂ 2.122- μ m imaging survey of Taurus-Auriga-Perseus - I. NGC 1333, L1455, L1448 and B1. *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomy Society*, 387:954–968, July 2008. doi: 10.1111/j.1365-2966.2008.13247.x.
- G. Duchêne, J. Bouvier, S. Bontemps, P. André, and F. Motte. Multiple protostellar systems. I. A deep near infrared survey of Taurus and Ophiuchus protostellar objects. *Astronomy and Astrophysics*, 427:651–665, Nov. 2004. doi: 10.1051/0004-6361:20041209.
- S. A. Dzib, L. Loinard, L. F. Rodríguez, A. J. Mioduszewski, G. N. Ortiz-León, M. A. Kounkel, G. Pech, J. L. Rivera, R. M. Torres, A. F. Boden, L. Hartmann, N. J. Evans, II, C. Briceño, and J. Tobin. The Gould’s Belt Very Large Array Survey. IV. The Taurus-Auriga Complex. *The Astrophysical Journal*, 801:91, Mar. 2015. doi: 10.1088/0004-637X/801/2/91.

- C. Eiroa and M. M. Casali. The Serpens sources SVS 4 and FIRS 1 - New results from infrared images. *Astronomy and Astrophysics*, 223:L17–L19, Oct. 1989.
- J. A. Eisner. Disk Masses at the End of the Main Accretion Phase: CARMA Observations and Multi-wavelength Modeling of Class I Protostars. *The Astrophysical Journal*, 755:23, Aug. 2012. doi: 10.1088/0004-637X/755/1/23.
- J. A. Eisner, L. A. Hillenbrand, J. M. Carpenter, and S. Wolf. Constraining the Evolutionary Stage of Class I Protostars: Multiwavelength Observations and Modeling. *The Astrophysical Journal*, 635:396–421, Dec. 2005. doi: 10.1086/497161.
- M. L. Enoch, K. E. Young, J. Glenn, N. J. Evans, II, S. Golwala, A. I. Sargent, P. Harvey, J. Aguirre, A. Goldin, D. Haig, T. L. Huard, A. Lange, G. Laurent, P. Maloney, P. Mauskopf, P. Rossinot, and J. Sayers. Bolocam Survey for 1.1 mm Dust Continuum Emission in the c2d Legacy Clouds. I. Perseus. *The Astrophysical Journal*, 638:293–313, Feb. 2006. doi: 10.1086/498678.
- M. L. Enoch, N. J. Evans, II, A. I. Sargent, and J. Glenn. Properties of the Youngest Protostars in Perseus, Serpens, and Ophiuchus. *The Astrophysical Journal*, 692:973–997, Feb. 2009. doi: 10.1088/0004-637X/692/2/973.
- N. J. Evans, II, L. E. Allen, G. A. Blake, A. C. A. Boogert, T. Bourke, P. M. Harvey, J. E. Kessler, D. W. Koerner, C. W. Lee, L. G. Mundy, P. C. Myers, D. L. Padgett, K. Pontoppidan, A. I. Sargent, K. R. Stapelfeldt, E. F. van Dishoeck, C. H. Young, and K. E. Young. From Molecular Cores to Planet-forming Disks: An SIRTf Legacy Program. *Publications of the ASP*, 115:965–980, Aug. 2003. doi: 10.1086/376697.
- E. C. Fayolle, K. I. Öberg, R. T. Garrod, E. F. van Dishoeck, and S. E. Bisschop. Complex organic molecules in organic-poor massive young stellar objects. *Astronomy and Astrophysics*, 576:A45, Apr. 2015. doi: 10.1051/0004-6361/201323114.

- E. D. Feigelson and P. I. Nelson. Statistical methods for astronomical data with upper limits. I - Univariate distributions. *The Astrophysical Journal*, 293:192–206, June 1985. doi: 10.1086/163225.
- T. Ferradaz, Y. Bénilan, N. Fray, A. Jolly, M. Schwell, M. C. Gazeau, and H.-W. Jochims. Temperature-dependent photoabsorption cross-sections of cyanoacetylene and diacetylene in the mid- and vacuum-UV: Application to Titan’s atmosphere. *Planetary and Space Science*, 57:10–22, Jan. 2009. doi: 10.1016/j.pss.2008.10.005.
- M. Fournier. PhD thesis, Université de Rennes, 2014.
- A. Fuente, J. Cernicharo, A. Barcia, and J. Gomez-Gonzalez. Sulphur-bearing molecules in dark clouds. *Astronomy and Astrophysics*, 231:151–158, May 1990.
- K. Fukuzawa and Y. Osamura. Molecular Orbital Study of Neutral-Neutral Reactions concerning HC₃N Formation in Interstellar Space. *The Astrophysical Journal*, 489:113–121, Nov. 1997. doi: 10.1086/304782.
- K. Fukuzawa, Y. Osamura, and H. F. Schaefer, III. Are Neutral-Neutral Reactions Effective for the Carbon-Chain Growth of Cyanopolyynes and Polyacetylenes in Interstellar Space? *The Astrophysical Journal*, 505:278–285, Sept. 1998. doi: 10.1086/306168.
- G. A. Fuller, P. C. Myers, W. J. Welch, P. F. Goldsmith, W. D. Langer, B. G. Campbell, S. Guilloteau, and R. W. Wilson. Anatomy of the Barnard 5 core. *The Astrophysical Journal*, 376:135–149, July 1991. doi: 10.1086/170262.
- E. Furlan, M. McClure, N. Calvet, L. Hartmann, P. D’Alessio, W. J. Forrest, D. M. Watson, K. I. Uchida, B. Sargent, J. D. Green, and T. L. Herter. Spitzer IRS Spectra and Envelope Models of Class I Protostars in Taurus. *The Astrophysical Journal, Supplement*, 176:184–215, May 2008. doi: 10.1086/527301.

- R. T. Garrod and E. Herbst. Formation of methyl formate and other organic species in the warm-up phase of hot molecular cores. *Astronomy and Astrophysics*, 457:927–936, Oct. 2006. doi: 10.1051/0004-6361:20065560.
- R. T. Garrod, S. L. Widicus Weaver, and E. Herbst. Complex Chemistry in Star-forming Regions: An Expanded Gas-Grain Warm-up Chemical Model. *The Astrophysical Journal*, 682:283-302, July 2008. doi: 10.1086/588035.
- E. L. Gibb, D. C. B. Whittet, W. A. Schutte, A. C. A. Boogert, J. E. Chiar, P. Ehrenfreund, P. A. Gerakines, J. V. Keane, A. G. G. M. Tielens, E. F. van Dishoeck, and O. Kerkhof. An Inventory of Interstellar Ices toward the Embedded Protostar W33A. *The Astrophysical Journal*, 536:347–356, June 2000. doi: 10.1086/308940.
- F. Goesmann, H. Rosenbauer, J. H. Bredehöft, M. Cabane, P. Ehrenfreund, T. Gautier, C. Giri, H. Krüger, L. Le Roy, A. J. MacDermott, S. McKenna-Lawlor, U. J. Meierhenrich, G. M. M. Caro, F. Raulin, R. Roll, A. Steele, H. Steining, R. Sternberg, C. Szopa, W. Thiemann, and S. Ulamec. Organic compounds on comet 67P/Churyumov-Gerasimenko revealed by COSAC mass spectrometry. *Science*, 349(2), July 2015. doi: 10.1126/science.aab0689.
- P. F. Goldsmith and W. D. Langer. Population Diagram Analysis of Molecular Line Emission. *The Astrophysical Journal*, 517:209–225, May 1999. doi: 10.1086/307195.
- A. A. Goodman, R. M. Crutcher, C. Heiles, P. C. Myers, and T. H. Troland. Measurement of magnetic field strength in the dark cloud Barnard 1. *The Astrophysical Journal, Letters*, 338:L61–L64, Mar. 1989. doi: 10.1086/185401.
- R. J. Gould and E. E. Salpeter. The Interstellar Abundance of the Hydrogen Molecule. I. Basic Processes. *The Astrophysical Journal*, 138:393, Aug. 1963. doi: 10.1086/147654.

- D. M. Graninger, O. H. Wilkins, and K. I. Öberg. Carbon Chains and Methanol toward Embedded Protostars. *The Astrophysical Journal*, 819:140, Mar. 2016. doi: 10.3847/0004-637X/819/2/140.
- P. Gratier, L. Majumdar, M. Ohishi, E. Roueff, J. C. Loison, K. M. Hickson, and V. Wakelam. A New Reference Chemical Composition for TMC-1. *The Astrophysical Journal, Supplement*, 225:25, Aug. 2016. doi: 10.3847/0067-0049/225/2/25.
- R. Gredel, S. Lepp, A. Dalgarno, and E. Herbst. Cosmic-ray-induced photodissociation and photoionization rates of interstellar molecules. *The Astrophysical Journal*, 347:289–293, Dec. 1989. doi: 10.1086/168117.
- T. P. Greene and C. J. Lada. The Unusually Rich Infrared Emission-Line Spectrum of a Deeply Embedded Low-Luminosity Young Stellar Object. *The Astrophysical Journal*, 461:345, Apr. 1996. doi: 10.1086/177061.
- S. Guilloteau, L. Reboussin, A. Dutrey, E. Chapillon, V. Wakelam, V. Piétu, E. Di Folco, D. Semenov, and T. Henning. Chemistry in disks. X. The molecular content of protoplanetary disks in Taurus. *Astronomy and Astrophysics*, 592:A124, Aug. 2016. doi: 10.1051/0004-6361/201527088.
- T. I. Hasegawa, E. Herbst, and C. M. Leung. Models of gas-grain chemistry in dense interstellar clouds with complex organic molecules. *The Astrophysical Journal, Supplement*, 82:167–195, Sept. 1992. doi: 10.1086/191713.
- G. E. Hassel, E. Herbst, and R. T. Garrod. Modeling the Lukewarm Corino Phase: Is L1527 Unique? *The Astrophysical Journal*, 681:1385-1395, July 2008. doi: 10.1086/588185.
- G. E. Hassel, N. Harada, and E. Herbst. Carbon-chain Species in Warm-up Models. *The Astrophysical Journal*, 743:182, Dec. 2011. doi: 10.1088/0004-637X/743/2/182.

- J. Hatchell, G. A. Fuller, J. S. Richer, T. J. Harries, and E. F. Ladd. Star formation in Perseus. II. SEDs, classification, and lifetimes. *Astronomy and Astrophysics*, 468:1009–1024, June 2007. doi: 10.1051/0004-6361:20066466.
- G. Helou and D. W. Walker, editors. *Infrared astronomical satellite (IRAS) catalogs and atlases. Volume 7: The small scale structure catalog*, volume 7, 1988.
- E. Herbst and W. Klemperer. The Formation and Depletion of Molecules in Dense Interstellar Clouds. *The Astrophysical Journal*, 185:505–534, Oct. 1973. doi: 10.1086/152436.
- E. Herbst and C. M. Leung. Gas-phase production of complex hydrocarbons, cyanopolyynes, and related compounds in dense interstellar clouds. *The Astrophysical Journal, Supplement*, 69:271–300, Feb. 1989. doi: 10.1086/191314.
- E. Herbst and T. J. Millar. The Chemistry of Cold Interstellar Cores. *Imperial College Press*, pages 1–54, 2008.
- E. Herbst and E. F. van Dishoeck. Complex Organic Interstellar Molecules. *Annual Review of Astronomy and Astrophysics*, 47:427–480, Sept. 2009. doi: 10.1146/annurev-astro-082708-101654.
- J. Hilton and J. F. Lahulla. Distance measurements of LYNDs galactic dark nebulae. *Astronomy and Astrophysics, Supplement*, 113:325, Oct. 1995.
- Y. Hirahara, H. Suzuki, S. Yamamoto, K. Kawaguchi, N. Kaifu, M. Ohishi, S. Takano, S.-I. Ishikawa, and A. Masuda. Mapping observations of sulfur-containing carbon-chain molecules in Taurus Molecular Cloud 1 (TMC-1). *The Astrophysical Journal*, 394:539–551, Aug. 1992. doi: 10.1086/171605.
- N. Hirano, O. Kameya, H. Mikami, T. Umemoto, and S. Yamamoto. The Small-Scale

- Structure of the CO Outflow in Barnard 1. *The Astrophysical Journal*, 478:631–637, Mar. 1997. doi: 10.1086/303831.
- N. Hirano, S.-Y. Liu, H. Shang, P. T. P. Ho, H.-C. Huang, Y.-J. Kuan, M. J. McCaughrean, and Q. Zhang. SiO $J = 5-4$ in the HH 211 Protostellar Jet Imaged with the Submillimeter Array. *The Astrophysical Journal, Letters*, 636:L141–L144, Jan. 2006. doi: 10.1086/500201.
- T. Hirota, H. Maezawa, and S. Yamamoto. Molecular Line Observations of Carbon-Chain-Producing Regions L1495B and L1521B. *The Astrophysical Journal*, 617:399–405, Dec. 2004. doi: 10.1086/425261.
- M. R. Hogerheijde. From Infall to Rotation around Young Stellar Objects: A Transitional Phase with a 2000 AU Radius Contracting Disk? *The Astrophysical Journal*, 553:618–632, June 2001. doi: 10.1086/320972.
- M. R. Hogerheijde, E. F. van Dishoeck, G. A. Blake, and H. J. van Langevelde. Envelope Structure on 700 AU Scales and the Molecular Outflows of Low-Mass Young Stellar Objects. *The Astrophysical Journal*, 502:315–336, July 1998. doi: 10.1086/305885.
- T. L. Huard, P. C. Myers, D. C. Murphy, L. J. Crews, C. J. Lada, T. L. Bourke, A. Crapsi, N. J. Evans, II, D. W. McCarthy, Jr., and C. Kulesa. Deep Near-Infrared Observations of L1014: Revealing the Nature of the Core and Its Embedded Source. *The Astrophysical Journal*, 640:391–401, Mar. 2006. doi: 10.1086/498742.
- C. L. H. Hull, R. L. Plambeck, W. Kwon, G. C. Bower, J. M. Carpenter, R. M. Crutcher, J. D. Fiege, E. Franzmann, N. S. Hakobian, C. Heiles, M. Houde, A. M. Hughes, J. W. Lamb, L. W. Looney, D. P. Marrone, B. C. Matthews, T. Pillai, M. W. Pound, N. Rahman, G. Sandell, I. W. Stephens, J. J. Tobin, J. E. Vaillancourt, N. H. Volgenau, and M. C. H. Wright. TADPOL: A 1.3 mm Survey of Dust Polarization in Star-forming

- Cores and Regions. *The Astrophysical Journal, Supplement*, 213:13, July 2014. doi: 10.1088/0067-0049/213/1/13.
- N. Indriolo, L. M. Hobbs, K. H. Hinkle, and B. J. McCall. Interstellar Metastable Helium Absorption as a Probe of the Cosmic-ray Ionization Rate. *The Astrophysical Journal*, 703: 2131–2137, Oct. 2009. doi: 10.1088/0004-637X/703/2/2131.
- A. P. Jones. Dust evolution, a global view I. Nanoparticles, nascence, nitrogen and natural selection ... joining the dots. *Royal Society Open Science*, 3:160221, Dec. 2016. doi: 10.1098/rsos.160221.
- J. K. Jørgensen, F. L. Schöier, and E. F. van Dishoeck. Physical structure and CO abundance of low-mass protostellar envelopes. *Astronomy and Astrophysics*, 389:908–930, July 2002. doi: 10.1051/0004-6361:20020681.
- J. K. Jørgensen, P. M. Harvey, N. J. Evans, II, T. L. Huard, L. E. Allen, A. Porras, G. A. Blake, T. L. Bourke, N. Chapman, L. Cieza, D. W. Koerner, S.-P. Lai, L. G. Mundy, P. C. Myers, D. L. Padgett, L. Rebull, A. I. Sargent, W. Spiesman, K. R. Stapelfeldt, E. F. van Dishoeck, Z. Wahhaj, and K. E. Young. The Spitzer c2d Survey of Large, Nearby, Interstellar Clouds. III. Perseus Observed with IRAC. *The Astrophysical Journal*, 645:1246–1263, July 2006. doi: 10.1086/504373.
- J. K. Jørgensen, M. H. D. van der Wiel, A. Coutens, J. M. Lykke, H. S. P. Müller, E. F. van Dishoeck, H. Calcutt, P. Bjerke, T. L. Bourke, M. N. Drozdovskaya, C. Favre, E. C. Fayolle, R. T. Garrod, S. K. Jacobsen, K. I. Öberg, M. V. Persson, and S. F. Wampfler. The ALMA Protostellar Interferometric Line Survey (PILS). First results from an unbiased submillimeter wavelength line survey of the Class 0 protostellar binary IRAS 16293-2422 with ALMA. *Astronomy and Astrophysics*, 595:A117, Nov. 2016. doi: 10.1051/0004-6361/201628648.

- J. Juan, R. Bachiller, C. Koempe, and J. Martin-Pintado. High density structure of the L 1455 dark cloud. *Astronomy and Astrophysics*, 270:432–443, Mar. 1993.
- N. Kaifu, M. Ohishi, K. Kawaguchi, S. Saito, S. Yamamoto, T. Miyaji, K. Miyazawa, S.-I. Ishikawa, C. Noumaru, S. Harasawa, M. Okuda, and H. Suzuki. A 8.8–50GHz Complete Spectral Line Survey toward TMC-1 I. Survey Data. *Publications of the Astronomical Society of Japan*, 56:69–173, Feb. 2004. doi: 10.1093/pasj/56.1.69.
- R. I. Kaiser, C. Ochsenfeld, M. Head-Gordon, Y. T. Lee, and A. G. Suits. Crossed-beam reaction of carbon atoms with hydrocarbon molecules. III: Chemical dynamics of propynylidyne ($l\text{-C}_3\text{H}; X \text{ } ^2\Pi_j$) and cyclopropynylidyne ($c\text{-C}_3\text{H}; X \text{ } ^2B_2$) formation from reaction of $C(^3P_j)$ with acetylene, $C_2H_2(X \text{ } ^1\Sigma_g^+)$. *Journal of Chemical Physics*, 106:1729–1741, Feb. 1997. doi: 10.1063/1.474092.
- R. I. Kaiser, C. Ochsenfeld, M. Head-Gordon, and Y. T. Lee. Neutral-Neutral Reactions in the Interstellar Medium. II. Isotope Effects in the Formation of Linear and Cyclic C_3H and C_3D Radicals in Interstellar Environments. *The Astrophysical Journal*, 510:784–788, Jan. 1999. doi: 10.1086/306626.
- S. J. Kenyon, N. Calvet, and L. Hartmann. The embedded young stars in the Taurus-Auriga molecular cloud. I - Models for spectral energy distributions. *The Astrophysical Journal*, 414:676–694, Sept. 1993. doi: 10.1086/173114.
- H. Kirk, D. Johnstone, and M. Tafalla. Dynamics of Dense Cores in the Perseus Molecular Cloud. *The Astrophysical Journal*, 668:1042–1063, Oct. 2007. doi: 10.1086/521395.
- H. W. Kroto, C. Kirby, D. R. M. Walton, L. W. Avery, N. W. Broten, J. M. MacLeod, and T. Oka. The detection of cyanohexatriyne, $H(CC)_3CN$, in Heile’s Cloud 2. *The Astrophysical Journal, Letters*, 219:L133–L137, Feb. 1978. doi: 10.1086/182623.

- S. Kurtz, R. Cesaroni, E. Churchwell, P. Hofner, and C. M. Walmsley. Hot Molecular Cores and the Earliest Phases of High-Mass Star Formation. *Protostars and Planets IV*, pages 299–326, May 2000.
- C. J. Lada. Cold outflows, energetic winds, and enigmatic jets around young stellar objects. *Annual Review of Astronomy and Astrophysics*, 23:267–317, 1985. doi: 10.1146/annurev.aa.23.090185.001411.
- C. J. Lada. The Formation of Low Mass Stars: Observations. In C. J. Lada and N. D. Kylafis, editors, *NATO Advanced Science Institutes (ASI) Series C*, volume 342 of *NATO Advanced Science Institutes (ASI) Series C*, page 329, 1991.
- E. F. Ladd, E. A. Lada, and P. C. Myers. An infrared survey for embedded young stars in the Perseus molecular cloud complex. *The Astrophysical Journal*, 410:168–178, June 1993. doi: 10.1086/172735.
- E. F. Ladd, P. C. Myers, and A. A. Goodman. Dense cores in dark clouds. 10: Ammonia emission in the Perseus molecular cloud complex. *The Astrophysical Journal*, 433:117–130, Sept. 1994. doi: 10.1086/174629.
- C. M. Leung, M. L. Kutner, and K. N. Mead. On the origin and structure of isolated dark globules. *The Astrophysical Journal*, 262:583–589, Nov. 1982. doi: 10.1086/160450.
- L. Likkell, H. L. Dinerstein, D. F. Lester, A. Kindt, and K. Bartig. A Spectrophotometric Survey of K-Band Emission Lines in Planetary Nebulae. *Astronomical Journal*, 131:1515–1529, Mar. 2006. doi: 10.1086/500050.
- L. T. Little, P. W. Riley, and D. N. Matheson. Detection of the $J = 9-8$ transition of interstellar cyanodiacetylene. *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomy Society*, 181:33P–35P, Oct. 1977. doi: 10.1093/mnras/181.1.33P.

- J.-C. Loison and A. Bergeat. Rate constants and the H atom branching ratio of the reactions of the methylidyne radical with C_2H_2 , C_2H_4 , C_3H_4 , C_3H_6 and C_4H_8 . *Journal of Chemical Physics*, 11:655–664, 2009. doi: 10.1039/B812810C.
- K. L. Luhman, J. R. Stauffer, A. A. Muench, G. H. Rieke, E. A. Lada, J. Bouvier, and C. J. Lada. A Census of the Young Cluster IC 348. *The Astrophysical Journal*, 593:1093–1115, Aug. 2003. doi: 10.1086/376594.
- B. T. Lynds. Catalogue of Dark Nebulae. *The Astrophysical Journal, Supplement*, 7:1, May 1962. doi: 10.1086/190072.
- N. Marcelino, J. Cernicharo, M. Agúndez, E. Roueff, M. Gerin, J. Martín-Pintado, R. Mauersberger, and C. Thum. Discovery of Interstellar Propylene (CH_2CHCH_3): Missing Links in Interstellar Gas-Phase Chemistry. *The Astrophysical Journal, Letters*, 665:L127–L130, Aug. 2007. doi: 10.1086/521398.
- A. J. Markwick, T. J. Millar, and S. B. Charnley. On the Abundance Gradients of Organic Molecules along the TMC-1 Ridge. *The Astrophysical Journal*, 535:256–265, May 2000. doi: 10.1086/308814.
- F. Markwick-Kemper. The composition and evolution of dust in astrophysical environments. Spitzer Proposal, Mar. 2003.
- B. C. Matthews and C. D. Wilson. Magnetic Fields in Star-forming Molecular Clouds. V. Submillimeter Polarization of the Barnard 1 Dark Cloud. *The Astrophysical Journal*, 574:822–833, Aug. 2002. doi: 10.1086/341111.
- M. C. McCarthy, C. A. Gottlieb, H. Gupta, and P. Thaddeus. Laboratory and Astronomical Identification of the Negative Molecular Ion C_6H^- . *The Astrophysical Journal, Letters*, 652:L141–L144, Dec. 2006. doi: 10.1086/510238.

- M. J. McEwan, G. B. I. Scott, N. G. Adams, L. M. Babcock, R. Terzieva, and E. Herbst. New H and H₂ Reactions with Small Hydrocarbon Ions and Their Roles in Benzene Synthesis in Dense Interstellar Clouds. *The Astrophysical Journal*, 513:287–293, Mar. 1999. doi: 10.1086/306861.
- T. J. T. Moore and J. P. Emerson. Sensitive imaging polarimetry of the faint infrared reflection nebula in B5 IRS1. *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomy Society*, 259:381–394, Nov. 1992. doi: 10.1093/mnras/259.2.381.
- T. J. T. Moore and J. P. Emerson. Continued decline in the 1 - 5 μm brightness of B5 IRS1: 1990-93. *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomy Society*, 271:243–246, Nov. 1994. doi: 10.1093/mnras/271.1.243.
- F. Motte and P. André. The circumstellar environment of low-mass protostars: A millimeter continuum mapping survey. *Astronomy and Astrophysics*, 365:440–464, Jan. 2001. doi: 10.1051/0004-6361:20000072.
- S. Muller, F. Combes, M. Guélin, M. Gérin, S. Aalto, A. Beelen, J. H. Black, S. J. Curran, J. Darling, D. V-Trung, S. García-Burillo, C. Henkel, C. Horellou, S. Martín, I. Martí-Vidal, K. M. Menten, M. T. Murphy, J. Ott, T. Wiklind, and M. A. Zwaan. An ALMA Early Science survey of molecular absorption lines toward PKS 1830-211. Analysis of the absorption profiles. *Astronomy and Astrophysics*, 566:A112, June 2014. doi: 10.1051/0004-6361/201423646.
- M. J. Mumma and S. B. Charnley. The Chemical Composition of Comets-Emerging Taxonomies and Natal Heritage. *Annual Review of Astronomy and Astrophysics*, 49:471–524, Sept. 2011. doi: 10.1146/annurev-astro-081309-130811.
- P. C. Myers, G. A. Fuller, R. D. Mathieu, C. A. Beichman, P. J. Benson, R. E. Schild, and

- J. P. Emerson. Near-infrared and optical observations of IRAS sources in and near dense cores. *The Astrophysical Journal*, 319:340–357, Aug. 1987. doi: 10.1086/165458.
- D. A. Neufeld, B. Godard, M. Gerin, G. Pineau des Forêts, C. Bernier, E. Falgarone, U. U. Graf, R. Güsten, E. Herbst, P. Lesaffre, P. Schilke, P. Sonnentrucker, and H. Wiesemeyer. Sulphur-bearing molecules in diffuse molecular clouds: new results from SOFIA/GREAT and the IRAM 30 m telescope. *Astronomy and Astrophysics*, 577:A49, May 2015. doi: 10.1051/0004-6361/201425391.
- B. Nisini, T. Giannini, D. A. Neufeld, Y. Yuan, S. Antonucci, E. A. Bergin, and G. J. Melnick. Spitzer Spectral Line Mapping of Protostellar Outflows. II. H₂ Emission in L1157. *The Astrophysical Journal*, 724:69–79, Nov. 2010. doi: 10.1088/0004-637X/724/1/69.
- K. I. Öberg, A. C. A. Boogert, K. M. Pontoppidan, G. A. Blake, N. J. Evans, F. Lahuis, and E. F. van Dishoeck. The c2d Spitzer Spectroscopic Survey of Ices around Low-Mass Young Stellar Objects. III. CH₄. *The Astrophysical Journal*, 678:1032-1041, May 2008. doi: 10.1086/533432.
- K. I. Öberg, R. T. Garrod, E. F. van Dishoeck, and H. Linnartz. Formation rates of complex organics in UV irradiated CH₃OH-rich ices. I. Experiments. *Astronomy and Astrophysics*, 504:891–913, Sept. 2009. doi: 10.1051/0004-6361/200912559.
- K. I. Öberg, S. Bottinelli, J. K. Jørgensen, and E. F. van Dishoeck. A Cold Complex Chemistry Toward the Low-mass Protostar B1-b: Evidence for Complex Molecule Production in Ices. *The Astrophysical Journal*, 716:825–834, June 2010. doi: 10.1088/0004-637X/716/1/825.
- K. I. Öberg, A. C. A. Boogert, K. M. Pontoppidan, S. van den Broek, E. F. van Dishoeck, S. Bottinelli, G. A. Blake, and N. J. Evans, II. The Spitzer Ice Legacy: Ice Evolution

- from Cores to Protostars. *The Astrophysical Journal*, 740:109, Oct. 2011a. doi: 10.1088/0004-637X/740/2/109.
- K. I. Öberg, N. van der Marel, L. E. Kristensen, and E. F. van Dishoeck. Complex Molecules toward Low-mass Protostars: The Serpens Core. *The Astrophysical Journal*, 740:14, Oct. 2011b. doi: 10.1088/0004-637X/740/1/14.
- K. I. Öberg, T. Lauck, and D. Graninger. Complex Organic Molecules during Low-mass Star Formation: Pilot Survey Results. *The Astrophysical Journal*, 788:68, June 2014. doi: 10.1088/0004-637X/788/1/68.
- C. R. O'dell and Z. Wen. Postrefurbishment mission Hubble Space Telescope images of the core of the Orion Nebula: Proplyds, Herbig-Haro objects, and measurements of a circumstellar disk. *The Astrophysical Journal*, 436:194–202, Nov. 1994. doi: 10.1086/174892.
- M. Ohishi and N. Kaifu. Chemical and physical evolution of dark clouds. Molecular spectral line survey toward TMC-1. *Faraday Discussions*, 109:205, 1998. doi: 10.1039/a801058g.
- M. Ohishi, S.-I. Ishikawa, C. Yamada, H. Kanamori, W. M. Irvine, R. D. Brown, P. D. Godfrey, N. Kaifu, and H. Suzuki. Detection of a new carbon-chain molecule, CCO. *The Astrophysical Journal, Letters*, 380:L39–L42, Oct. 1991. doi: 10.1086/186168.
- G. N. Ortiz-León, L. Loinard, A. J. Mioduszewski, S. A. Dzib, L. F. Rodríguez, G. Pech, J. L. Rivera, R. M. Torres, A. F. Boden, L. Hartmann, N. J. Evans, II, C. Briceño, J. Tobin, M. A. Kounkel, and R. A. González-Lópezlira. The Gould's Belt Very Large Array Survey. II. The Serpens Region. *The Astrophysical Journal*, 805:9, May 2015. doi: 10.1088/0004-637X/805/1/9.
- Y. Oya, N. Sakai, Y. Watanabe, A. E. Higuchi, T. Hirota, A. López-Sepulcre, T. Sakai,

- Y. Aikawa, C. Ceccarelli, B. Lefloch, E. Caux, C. Vastel, C. Kahane, and S. Yamamoto. L483: Warm Carbon-chain Chemistry Source Harboring Hot Corino Activity. *The Astrophysical Journal*, 837:174, Mar. 2017. doi: 10.3847/1538-4357/aa6300.
- N. D. Parker. IRAS associations with dark clouds of opacity class 6. *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomy Society*, 235:139–150, Nov. 1988. doi: 10.1093/mnras/235.1.139.
- K. M. Pontoppidan, E. F. van Dishoeck, and E. Dartois. Mapping ices in protostellar environments on 1000 AU scales. Methanol-rich ice in the envelope of Serpens SMM 4. *Astronomy and Astrophysics*, 426:925–940, Nov. 2004. doi: 10.1051/0004-6361:20041276.
- S. S. Prasad and W. T. Huntress, Jr. Sulfur chemistry in dense interstellar clouds. *The Astrophysical Journal*, 260:590–598, Sept. 1982. doi: 10.1086/160280.
- S. S. Prasad and S. P. Tarafdar. UV radiation field inside dense clouds - Its possible existence and chemical implications. *The Astrophysical Journal*, 267:603–609, Apr. 1983. doi: 10.1086/160896.
- B. Reipurth, J. Bally, and D. Devine. Giant Herbig-Haro Flows. *The Astronomical Journal*, 114:2708, Dec. 1997. doi: 10.1086/118681.
- B. Reipurth, K. C. Yu, S. Heathcote, J. Bally, and L. F. Rodríguez. Hubble Space Telescope NICMOS Images of Herbig-Haro Energy Sources: [Fe II] Jets, Binarity, and Envelope Cavities. *The Astronomical Journal*, 120:1449–1466, Sept. 2000. doi: 10.1086/301510.
- T. P. Robitaille, B. A. Whitney, R. Indebetouw, K. Wood, and P. Denzmore. Interpreting Spectral Energy Distributions from Young Stellar Objects. I. A Grid of 200,000 YSO Model SEDs. *The Astrophysical Journal, Supplement*, 167:256–285, Dec. 2006. doi: 10.1086/508424.

- L. F. Rodríguez and B. Reipurth. VLA Detection of the Exciting Sources of HH 83, HH 117, HH 124, HH 192, HH 300, HH 366, and HH 375. *Revista Mexicana de Astronomía y Astrofísica*, 34:13, Apr. 1998.
- S. Saito, K. Kawaguchi, S. Yamamoto, M. Ohishi, H. Suzuki, and N. Kaifu. Laboratory detection and astronomical identification of a new free radical, CCS. *The Astrophysical Journal, Letters*, 317:L115–L118, June 1987. doi: 10.1086/184923.
- N. Sakai and S. Yamamoto. Warm Carbon-Chain Chemistry. *Chemical Reviews*, 113:1032–1041, Dec. 2013. doi: 10.1021/cr4001308.
- N. Sakai, T. Sakai, T. Hirota, and S. Yamamoto. Abundant Carbon-Chain Molecules toward the Low-Mass Protostar IRAS 04368+2557 in L1527. *The Astrophysical Journal*, 672:371–381, Jan. 2008. doi: 10.1086/523635.
- N. Sakai, T. Sakai, T. Hirota, M. Burton, and S. Yamamoto. Discovery of the Second Warm Carbon-Chain-Chemistry Source, IRAS15398 - 3359 in Lupus. *The Astrophysical Journal*, 697:769–786, May 2009. doi: 10.1088/0004-637X/697/1/769.
- A. I. Sargent and S. Beckwith. Kinematics of the circumstellar gas of HL Tauri and R Monocerotis. *The Astrophysical Journal*, 323:294–305, Dec. 1987. doi: 10.1086/165827.
- M. Saul, N. F. H. Tothill, and C. R. Purcell. Observations of Warm Carbon Chain Chemistry in NGC 3576. *The Astrophysical Journal*, 798:36, Jan. 2015. doi: 10.1088/0004-637X/798/1/36.
- E. F. Schlafly, G. Green, D. P. Finkbeiner, H.-W. Rix, E. F. Bell, W. S. Burgett, K. C. Chambers, P. W. Draper, K. W. Hodapp, N. Kaiser, E. A. Magnier, N. F. Martin, N. Metcalfe, P. A. Price, and J. L. Tonry. A Large Catalog of Accurate Distances to

- Molecular Clouds from PS1 Photometry. *The Astrophysical Journal*, 786:29, May 2014. doi: 10.1088/0004-637X/786/1/29.
- K. Seki, M. Yagi, M. He, J. B. Halpern, and H. Okabe. Reaction rates of the cn radical with diacetylene and dicyanoacetylene. *Chemical Physics Letters*, 258(5):657 – 662, 1996. ISSN 0009-2614. doi: [http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/0009-2614\(96\)00697-5](http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/0009-2614(96)00697-5).
- Y. L. Shirley, N. J. Evans, II, J. M. C. Rawlings, and E. M. Gregersen. Tracing the Mass during Low-Mass Star Formation. I. Submillimeter Continuum Observations. *The Astrophysical Journal, Supplement*, 131:249–271, Nov. 2000. doi: 10.1086/317358.
- Y. L. Shirley, M. J. Claussen, T. L. Bourke, C. H. Young, and G. A. Blake. The Detection and Characterization of Centimeter Radio Continuum Emission from the Low-Mass Protostar L1014-IRS. *The Astrophysical Journal*, 667:329–339, Sept. 2007. doi: 10.1086/520570.
- R. Silva, W. K. Gichuhi, C. Huang, M. B. Doyle, V. V. Kislov, A. M. Mebel, and A. G. Suits. H elimination and metastable lifetimes in the UV photoexcitation of diacetylene. *PNAS*, 105:12713–12718, Feb. 2008.
- T. Simon. XMM Observations of Two Quadrupolar Outflows. *The Astrophysical Journal*, 693:1803–1813, Mar. 2009. doi: 10.1088/0004-637X/693/2/1803.
- D. Smith. The Ion Chemistry of Interstellar Clouds. *Chemical Reviews*, 92:1473–1485, Nov. 1992.
- H. A. Smith, J. Fischer, T. R. Geballe, and P. R. Schwartz. Infrared line observations of low-luminosity outflow sources. *The Astrophysical Journal*, 316:265–274, May 1987. doi: 10.1086/165198.
- I. W. M. Smith, E. Herbst, and Q. Chang. Rapid neutral-neutral reactions at low tempera-

- tures: a new network and first results for TMC-1. *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomy Society*, 350:323–330, May 2004. doi: 10.1111/j.1365-2966.2004.07656.x.
- R. L. Snell, R. B. Loren, and R. L. Plambeck. Observations of CO in L1551 - Evidence for stellar wind driven shocks. *The Astrophysical Journal, Letters*, 239:L17–L22, July 1980. doi: 10.1086/183283.
- K. M. Strom, S. E. Strom, S. Edwards, S. Cabrit, and M. F. Skrutskie. Circumstellar material associated with solar-type pre-main-sequence stars - A possible constraint on the timescale for planet building. *The Astronomical Journal*, 97:1451–1470, May 1989. doi: 10.1086/115085.
- A. Stutz, R. Launhardt, H. Linz, O. Krause, T. Henning, J. Kainulainen, M. Nielbock, J. Steinacker, and P. André. Dust-temperature of an isolated star-forming cloud: Herschel observations of the Bok globule CB244. *Astronomy and Astrophysics*, 518:L87, July 2010. doi: 10.1051/0004-6361/201014537.
- H. Suzuki, S. Yamamoto, M. Ohishi, N. Kaifu, S.-I. Ishikawa, Y. Hirahara, and S. Takano. A survey of CCS, HC₃N, HC₅N, and NH₃ toward dark cloud cores and their production chemistry. *The Astrophysical Journal*, 392:551–570, June 1992. doi: 10.1086/171456.
- M. Tafalla and R. Bachiller. Molecules in Bipolar Outflows. In J. Cernicharo and R. Bachiller, editors, *The Molecular Universe*, volume 280 of *IAU Symposium*, pages 88–102, Dec. 2011. doi: 10.1017/S1743921311024896.
- C. Terquem and C. Bertout. Tidally induced WARPS in T Tauri discs - II. A parametric study of spectral energy distributions. *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomy Society*, 279:415–428, Mar. 1996. doi: 10.1093/mnras/279.2.415.
- R. M. Torres, L. Loinard, A. J. Mioduszewski, and L. F. Rodríguez. VLBA Determination

- of the Distance to Nearby Star-forming Regions. II. Hubble 4 and HDE 283572 in Taurus. *The Astrophysical Journal*, 671:1813–1819, Dec. 2007. doi: 10.1086/522924.
- C. H. Townes and A. L. Schawlow. *Microwave Spectroscopy*. 1955.
- H. Ungerechts and P. Thaddeus. A CO survey of the dark nebulae in Perseus, Taurus, and Auriga. *The Astrophysical Journal, Supplement*, 63:645–660, Mar. 1987. doi: 10.1086/191176.
- E. F. van Dishoeck and G. A. Blake. Chemical Evolution of Star-Forming Regions. *Annual Review of Astronomy and Astrophysics*, 36:317–368, 1998. doi: 10.1146/annurev.astro.36.1.317.
- R. Visser, E. F. van Dishoeck, S. D. Doty, and C. P. Dullemond. The chemical history of molecules in circumstellar disks. I. Ices. *Astronomy and Astrophysics*, 495:881–897, Mar. 2009. doi: 10.1051/0004-6361/200810846.
- R. Visser, E. F. van Dishoeck, and S. D. Doty. Chemical History of Molecules in Circumstellar Disks. In J. Cernicharo and R. Bachiller, editors, *The Molecular Universe*, volume 280 of *IAU Symposium*, pages 138–148, Dec. 2011. doi: 10.1017/S1743921311024938.
- J. Walawender, J. Bally, H. Kirk, and D. Johnstone. Multiple Outflows and Protostars in Barnard 1. *The Astronomical Journal*, 130:1795–1804, Oct. 2005. doi: 10.1086/432971.
- J. Walawender, J. Bally, J. D. Francesco, J. Jørgensen, and K. . Getman. *NGC 1333: A Nearby Burst of Star Formation*, page 346. Dec. 2008.
- Y. Watanabe, N. Sakai, A. López-Sepulcre, R. Furuya, T. Sakai, T. Hirota, S.-Y. Liu, Y.-N. Su, and S. Yamamoto. Spectral Line Survey toward the Young Massive Protostar NGC 2264 CMM3 in the 4 mm, 3 mm, and 0.8 mm Bands. *The Astrophysical Journal*, 809:162, Aug. 2015. doi: 10.1088/0004-637X/809/2/162.

- D. M. Watson, F. Kemper, N. Calvet, L. D. Keller, E. Furlan, L. Hartmann, W. J. Forrest, C. H. Chen, K. I. Uchida, J. D. Green, B. Sargent, G. C. Sloan, T. L. Herter, B. R. Brandl, J. R. Houck, J. Najita, P. D'Alessio, P. C. Myers, D. J. Barry, P. Hall, and P. W. Morris. Mid-infrared Spectra of Class I Protostars in Taurus. *The Astrophysical Journal, Supplement*, 154:391–395, Sept. 2004. doi: 10.1086/422918.
- W. D. Watson. The Rate of Formation of Interstellar Molecules by Ion-Molecule Reactions. *The Astrophysical Journal, Letters*, 183:L17, July 1973. doi: 10.1086/181242.
- B. A. Whitney, S. J. Kenyon, and M. Gómez. Near-Infrared Imaging Polarimetry of Embedded Young Stars in the Taurus-Auriga Molecular Cloud. *The Astrophysical Journal*, 485:703–734, Aug. 1997. doi: 10.1086/304454.
- D. C. B. Whittet, editor. *Dust in the galactic environment*, 2003.
- B. A. Wilking, S. Bontemps, R. E. Schuler, T. P. Greene, and P. André. Infrared Properties of Weak Radio Sources in the ρ Ophiuchi Molecular Cloud. *The Astrophysical Journal*, 551:357–366, Apr. 2001. doi: 10.1086/320067.
- S. Yamamoto, S. Saito, K. Kawaguchi, N. Kaifu, and H. Suzuki. Laboratory detection of a new carbon-chain molecule C₃S and its astronomical identification. *The Astrophysical Journal, Letters*, 317:L119–L121, June 1987. doi: 10.1086/184924.
- H.-W. Yen, S. Takakuwa, N. Ohashi, and P. T. P. Ho. Unveiling the Evolutionary Sequence from Infalling Envelopes to Keplerian Disks around Low-mass Protostars. *The Astrophysical Journal*, 772:22, July 2013. doi: 10.1088/0004-637X/772/1/22.
- C. H. Young, J. K. Jørgensen, Y. L. Shirley, J. Kauffmann, T. Huard, S.-P. Lai, C. W. Lee, A. Crapsi, T. L. Bourke, C. P. Dullemond, T. Y. Brooke, A. Porras, W. Spiesman, L. E. Allen, G. A. Blake, N. J. Evans, II, P. M. Harvey, D. W. Koerner, L. G. Mundy, P. C.

- Myers, D. L. Padgett, A. I. Sargent, K. R. Stapelfeldt, E. F. van Dishoeck, F. Bertoldi, N. Chapman, L. Cieza, C. H. DeVries, N. A. Ridge, and Z. Wahhaj. A “Starless” Core that Isn’t: Detection of a Source in the L1014 Dense Core with the Spitzer Space Telescope. *The Astrophysical Journal, Supplement*, 154:396–401, Sept. 2004. doi: 10.1086/422818.
- K. E. Young, C. H. Young, S.-P. Lai, M. M. Dunham, and N. J. Evans, II. The Spitzer c2d Survey of Large, Nearby, Interstellar Clouds. XII. The Perseus YSO Population as Observed with IRAC and MIPS. *The Astronomical Journal*, 150:40, Aug. 2015. doi: 10.1088/0004-6256/150/2/40.
- A. Zanchet, M. Agúndez, V. J. Herrero, A. Aguado, and O. Roncero. Sulfur Chemistry in the Interstellar Medium: The Effect of Vibrational Excitation of H₂ in the Reaction S⁺+H₂ →SH⁺+H. *The Astronomical Journal*, 146:125, Nov. 2013. doi: 10.1088/0004-6256/146/5/125.